

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Harnessing the biomimetic effect of macromolecular crowding in the cell-derived model of clubfoot fibrosis

Martina Doubková^{1,2,}, Jarmila Knitlová^{1,3}, David Vondrášek⁴, Adam Eckhardt⁵, Tomáš*

Novotný^{6,7}, Martin Ošťádal⁸, Elena Filová¹, Lucie Bačáková¹

¹ Laboratory of Biomaterials and Tissue Engineering, Institute of Physiology of the Czech
Academy of Sciences, Videnska 1083, 142 00 Prague 4, Czech Republic

² Second Faculty of Medicine, Charles University, V Uvalu 84, 150 06 Prague 5, Czech
Republic

³ Faculty of Science, Charles University, Albertov 6, 128 00 Prague 2, Czech Republic

⁴ Laboratory of Biomathematics, Institute of Physiology of the Czech Academy of Sciences,
Videnska 1083, 142 00 Prague 4, Czech Republic

⁵ Laboratory of Translational Metabolism, Institute of Physiology of the Czech Academy of
Sciences, Videnska 1083, 142 00 Prague 4, Czech Republic

⁶ Department of Orthopaedics, Masaryk Hospital, Socialni Pece 3316/12A, 401 13 Usti nad
Labem, Czech Republic

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

⁷ Department of Histology and Embryology, Second Faculty of Medicine, Charles University,
V Uvalu 84, 150 06 Prague 5, Czech Republic

⁸ Department of Orthopaedics, University Hospital Bulovka, Charles University, Budinova
67/2, 180 81 Prague 8, Czech Republic

* Email: Martina.Doubkova@fgu.cas.cz

ABSTRACT: Fibrotic changes in paediatric clubfoot provide an opportunity to improve corrective therapy and prevent relapses with targeted drugs. This study defines the parameters of clubfoot fibrosis and presents a unique analysis of a simple pseudo-3D *in vitro* model for disease-specific high-throughput drug screening experiments. The model combines clubfoot-derived fibroblasts with a biomimetic cultivation environment induced by the water-soluble polymers Ficoll and Polyvinylpyrrolidone, utilising the principle of macromolecular crowding. We achieved higher conversion of soluble collagen into insoluble collagen, accelerated formation of the extracellular matrix layer and upregulated fibrosis-related genes in the mixed Ficoll environment. To test the model, we evaluated the effect of a potential anti-fibrotic drug, minoxidil, emphasizing collagen content and cross-linking. While the model amplified overall collagen deposition, minoxidil effectively blocked the expression of lysyl hydroxylases, which are responsible for the increased occurrence of specific collagen crosslinking in various fibrotic tissues. This limited the formation of collagen cross-link in

1
2
3 both the model and control environments. Our findings provide a tool for expanding
4
5
6 preclinical research for clubfoot and similar fibroproliferative conditions.
7
8
9

10 KEYWORDS: fibrosis model; idiopathic clubfoot; collagen; cross-linking; drug screening;
11
12 minoxidil
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Introduction

Idiopathic clubfoot (*Talipes equinovarus*) is a common congenital lower limb deformity with a complex multifactorial aetiology that is present in 1-2 in 1,000 newborns worldwide.¹ This defect comprises fixation of the foot in plantar flexion with inward rotation of the sole, which leads to the deformation of soft and hard tissues,^{2,3} resulting in moderate to severe mobility impairment. The stiffness of the deformed tissues poses a challenge for the main corrective methods of systematic serial manipulation, casting, and bracing.⁴ The Ponseti corrective method usually achieves excellent results, provided that the regimen is followed correctly. Unfortunately, approx. 30 % of patients experience a relapse within 5 years after starting treatment, mainly due to patient and parental non-compliance.^{5,6} Patients must therefore repeatedly undergo the burden of corrective treatment with a decreasing chance of success or a surgical release may even be considered.⁷ When relapsed clubfoot is resistant to the main corrective treatment method, further treatment could be attempted with an adjunctive pharmaceutical approach. For example, the application of botulinum toxin A injections was proposed, but it failed to demonstrate an adequate positive effect on important aspects of the standard treatment and failed to prevent relapses of isolated idiopathic clubfoot during clinical trials.^{8,9} However, this neurotoxin has proved to be effective in the treatment of spastic clubfoot,¹⁰ where the contracture had different underlying causes.

The unclear aetiology provides challenges in research on potential adjuvant or alternative treatment, but previous analyses of tissue biopsies of prenatal^{2,11} and relapsed idiopathic clubfeet¹²⁻¹⁵ suggest the presence of fibrotic changes localized in the stiff, contracted tissue on the medial side (CF-M side). More recent reports on the differences between the medial side

1
2
3 tissue and the non-contracted lateral side (CF-L side) tissue have come primarily from work
4
5 carried out by our research group, and are in agreement with earlier studies. The affected
6
7 medial side tissue exhibits increased amounts of collagen type I, III, V, and VI,¹⁶⁻¹⁸
8
9 fibronectin, tenascin-C,^{16,17,19} transforming growth factor-beta-induced protein (TGF- β ip),^{16,17}
10
11 transforming growth factor-beta (TGF- β), smooth muscle α -actin,¹⁹ increased collagen cross-
12
13 linking,¹⁸ and expression of cross-linking enzymes lysyl oxidase and lysyl oxidase-like 2.¹⁹ In
14
15 addition, quantitative mechanical analysis of the clubfoot tissue has suggested relative
16
17 stiffness of the medial side connective tissue compared to the lateral side.²⁰ Together, these
18
19 indications make the medial side a possible candidate for targeted treatment.
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27

28 The accumulation of extracellular matrix (ECM) proteins, especially fibrillar collagens, and
29
30 growth factors regulating cell behaviour to drive the deposition of ECM are typical in
31
32 connective tissue diseases such as Dupuytren's contracture, Peyronie's disease, hypertrophic
33
34 scars and keloids (for a review, see Siani *et al.*²¹). The underlying process in these conditions
35
36 is fibrosis. Only a small number of studies have approached this problem in clubfoot by
37
38 suggesting the targeted application of anti-fibrotic agents. Researchers have suggested
39
40 influencing the tissue properties through the downregulation of growth factors TGF-beta and
41
42 platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF)¹⁴ or beta-catenin,¹⁵ which is part of a signalling
43
44 pathway in crosstalk with TGF-beta signalling. In contrast, our research group has focused on
45
46 reducing cross-link formation in the produced ECM, which contributes to tissue stiffening by
47
48 inhibiting enzymes acting in post-translational modifications of collagen, i.e. lysyl
49
50 hydroxylases²² and lysyl oxidase.¹⁸ In addition to standard cell culture, we have employed
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 floating collagen gels with embedded cells to simulate the studied anti-fibrotic drug effects on
4
5
6 tissue-like contraction exerted by the traction forces of clubfoot-derived cells.^{18,22} However,
7
8
9 the studies performed by other groups have been conducted entirely in conventional 2D cell
10
11 cultures.

12
13 Fibroblasts and other cells *in vivo* produce and are surrounded by their specific ECM
14
15 microenvironment, which profoundly affects their phenotype and function. Tissue engineering
16
17 focuses constantly on modulating various physical properties of the microenvironment (such
18
19 as its topography or stiffness) and the chemical composition of the environment, which
20
21 provide important cues for cell behaviour. Especially in the investigation of fibrotic
22
23 conditions, the dilute environment of a standard *in vitro* monolayer cell culture is not ideal for
24
25 the deposition of ECM. This is primarily due to impaired collagen deposition as a result of the
26
27 slow enzymatic conversion of procollagen to collagen.²³ The phenomenon of macromolecular
28
29 crowding (MMC) can be conveniently used to mimic the dense physiological environment,
30
31 where the concentration of macromolecules is noticeably higher. The addition of specific inert
32
33 macromolecules into the culture media induces an effect of excluded volume, limiting the
34
35 space that can be accessed by other molecules, slowing their diffusion and facilitating
36
37 enhanced ECM deposition *in vitro*.^{23,24} MMC has been observed to affect the aggregation and
38
39 interaction of many ECM molecules, accelerating and increasing their deposition, affecting
40
41 stem cell differentiation, affecting the regulation of gene expression, promoting cell signalling
42
43 and increasing enzyme activity (for a comprehensive review, see Tsiapalis *et* Zeugolis²⁵).

44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55 The concept of MMC in cell culture is not entirely new,^{26,27} but interest in its research
56
57 applications has gradually increased in recent years, particularly in the field of tissue
58
59
60

1
2
3 engineering and drug discovery.^{24,28–35} Recent studies have utilised MMC to analyse the
4
5 effects of anti-fibrotic agents with or without simultaneous stimulation of cells by pro-fibrotic
6
7 growth factors.^{29,32,36,37} MMCs have been successfully applied to cultures of mesenchymal
8
9 stem cells,^{30,38–41} lung fibroblasts,^{29,32,35} dermal fibroblasts,^{33,38,42–44} fibroblasts from
10
11 hypertrophic scars,²⁸ tenocytes,^{45,46} and fibroblasts from the cornea.³¹ The most commonly
12
13 used macromolecular crowders include Dextran, Dextran sulfate, Ficoll, Carrageenan and
14
15 Polyvinylpyrrolidone.
16
17
18
19

20
21 *In vitro* cell culture with the application of MMC allows the creation of a biomimetic
22
23 environment mimicking the properties of the extracellular environment *in vivo*. The
24
25 behaviour of cells isolated from clubfoot in the MMC environment has not yet been
26
27 investigated. Although there have been studies aiming to establish an animal model of
28
29 clubfoot,^{47,48} no suitable *in vivo* model is yet available. It is therefore desirable to improve the
30
31 *in vitro* experimental conditions for performing relevant analyses when carrying out research
32
33 on adjuvant drug treatment.
34
35
36
37
38

39
40 The present study aimed to investigate the effect of macromolecular crowding (MMC) on
41
42 primary fibroblast cell cultures isolated from the tissues of patients after surgery for relapsed
43
44 idiopathic clubfoot. In the first part of the study, we aimed to develop an *in vitro* model based
45
46 on clubfoot-derived cells cultured under MMC conditions that emulates the fibrotic
47
48 environment in clubfoot, emphasizing collagen synthesis and deposition. In the second part of
49
50 the study, we aimed to explore the environment induced by MMC in an anti-fibrotic drug
51
52 screening setup with minoxidil, an inhibitor of lysyl hydroxylases.⁴⁹
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 Lysyl hydroxylases (more specifically isoform 2; LH2) are the enzymes responsible for the
4 increased occurrence of the specific collagen cross-linking (pyridinoline cross-links) observed
5
6 in various fibrotic tissues, including hypertrophic scars and Dupuytren's contracture.⁵⁰⁻⁵²
7
8 Inhibition of lysyl hydroxylase leads to a change in the type and the amount of cross-linking
9
10 between collagen type I fibers, resulting in a less stiff and more easily degradable ECM.⁵³
11
12 These properties of minoxidil could reduce tissue stiffness and contraction, making it a good
13
14 candidate for developing potential adjuvant pharmacological therapy to accompany the
15
16 standard treatment for relapsed clubfoot.
17
18
19
20
21
22

23
24 We have selected the two most commonly used crowders (Ficol70/Ficol400 mix and
25
26 Polyvinylpyrrolidone) and for the first time we have compared the effect of a wide range of
27
28 their concentrations (FVO 4%-54% in culture medium) simulating different physiological
29
30 environments³⁸ on cell cultures of clubfoot-derived fibroblasts (CF-M, CF-L). Normal human
31
32 fibroblasts (NHDFs) were used as a control. We evaluated the proliferation, viability, and
33
34 collagen production of the three cell types, with regard to the morphology and the maturation
35
36 of the deposited collagen fibers. In addition, we examined the effect of the culture medium
37
38 with the best-performing MMC environment on the gene expression of selected extracellular
39
40 matrix proteins and enzymes involved in post-translational modifications of collagen. To
41
42 validate the model pro-fibrotic conditions, we compared the data with the analyses of clubfoot
43
44 tissue. We also monitored the phases of collagen deposition in the form of soluble and
45
46 insoluble fractions in the extracellular matrix (ECM) and the amount of pyridinoline and
47
48 deoxypyridinoline cross-links in ECM cell layers. Finally, we tested the performance of
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 minoxidil, an inhibitor of lysyl hydroxylases, in the established MMC environment in
4
5
6 separate experiments.

8 **Methods**

10 **Biological samples and cell isolation**

11
12
13 The primary fibroblast cell cultures used in this study were isolated from tissue samples of
14
15
16 7 patients (5 males, 2 females; median age 4.3 years, SD=2.4; Table S1, Supporting
17
18 Information Section 1) treated for idiopathic congenital *talipes equinovarus* (ICTEV; further
19
20 referred to as clubfoot, CF). All of these patients had previously been treated using the Ponseti
21
22 method. Two tissue samples were harvested from the patients during surgery on relapsed
23
24 clubfoot after unsuccessful Ponseti treatment. Samples from the medial side of the foot (M-
25
26 side; CF-M) represent contracted fibrotic tissue localised between the medial malleolus, the
27
28 *sustentaculum tali* and the navicular bone. Samples from the lateral side of the foot (L-side;
29
30 CF-L) represent non-contracted tissue from the surface of the calcaneocuboid joint. All tissue
31
32 samples were processed within one hour after surgical excision by mincing and enzymatic
33
34 digestion to isolate the primary cell cultures. The process of isolation and characterisation of
35
36 the obtained cell culture was the same as we described in our previous study. Briefly, the cell
37
38 cultures comprised approximately 96% fibroblasts, less than 3% myofibroblasts, less than 3%
39
40 fibrocytes, less than 0.1% of vascular muscle cells, and no endothelial cells.²² Cell passages 1
41
42 to 3 were used in the experiments.

43
44
45 The tissue samples embedded in paraffin used for histological staining presented here were
46
47 collected previously for the study of Novotny *et al.*¹⁹ and are described in the appropriate
48
49 section.

1
2
3 The research was carried out under the Declaration of Helsinki (1964) and with the
4 approval of the ethics committee of the participating institutions (University Hospital
5
6 Bulovka, Ev. No. 1.6.2021/10070/EK-Z, June 2021; Institute of Physiology of the Czech
7
8 Academy of Sciences, project No. NU22-10-00072, June 2021). Parents or legally designated
9
10 representatives of all patients provided their written informed consent to participate. This
11
12 study is analytical, prospective, level of evidence IIb.
13
14
15
16
17

18 **Reagents used to induce an MMC-based biomimetic cell culture microenvironment**

19
20
21 The reagents used to create an experimental cell culture environment, and their final
22
23 concentrations, are summarised in this section. Neutral Ficoll and Polyvinylpyrrolidone were
24
25 selected to induce macromolecular crowding in the cell culture medium. The final
26
27 concentrations of the compounds were scaled to mimic the molecular crowding (MMC) of the
28
29 physiological environments according to the % fractional volume occupancy (FVO, v/v)
30
31 occupied by them in the culture medium, as referenced by Rashid *et al.*³⁸ Ficoll PM 70 kDa
32
33 (F2878, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) and Ficoll PM 400 kDa (F4375, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) were
34
35 used to create a model of mixed crowding (Ficoll mix) at FVO 4%, 9%, 18%, 36% and 54%.
36
37 Polyvinylpyrrolidone 40 kDa (PVP40, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) was used at FVO 9%, 18%,
38
39 36%, and 54% (Tab. 1).
40
41
42
43
44
45

46
47 Compounds for MMC were diluted in DMEM medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Gibco,
48
49 Waltham, MA, USA; Cat. No. 52100-021) with 25 mM HEPES and were filtered through an
50
51 SFCA 0.45 µm filter (431220, Corning, New York, USA). Then 40 µg/mL of gentamicin (Lek
52
53 Pharmaceuticals, Ljubljana, Slovenia) and 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS; Thermo Fisher
54
55 Scientific, Gibco, Waltham, MA, USA; Cat. No. 10270-106) were added in a volume
56
57
58
59
60

accounted for in the calculation of the final concentration of MMC compounds. L-ascorbic acid-2-phosphate trisodium salt (Asc-2P; 49752, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) at 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ was added to each of the MMC media to stimulate collagen synthesis.

Table 1: Groups of macromolecular crowders (MMC) diluted in media for the experiments.

% FVO	Ficoll mix		Polyvinylpyrrolidone
	Ficoll 70	Ficoll 400	PVP
4	8.34 mg/mL	5.56 mg/mL	---
9	18.75 mg/mL	12.5 mg/mL	10.75 mg/mL
18	37.50 mg/mL	25.00 mg/mL	21.50 mg/mL
36	75.00 mg/mL	50.00 mg/mL	43.00 mg/mL
54	112.50 mg/mL	75.00 mg/mL	64.50 mg/mL

Anti-fibrotic drug treatment

Only the 18% FVO concentration of the Ficoll mix (Fc18) was used in the drug testing experiments. The compound was diluted as described above, with the same supplements, and was sterilised with an SFCA 0.20 μm filter (431219, Corning, New York, USA). Minoxidil (MXD) (M4145, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) was dissolved in 96% ethanol (EtOH) to a stock solution of 119 mM, and was stored at -20°C in aliquots. The working concentrations of MXD (0 mM, 0.25 mM, 0.5 mM, 0.75 mM, 1 mM, 2 mM) were diluted immediately before each experiment in a complete medium with or without MMC. Fresh media were prepared before each experiment.

Cell culture

1
2
3 Primary fibroblast cells from the medial and lateral side of clubfoot (CF-M, CF-L) were
4 expanded in DMEM medium with 25 mM HEPES and 20% fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 40
5
6
7
8 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ gentamicin in an incubator (37°C , 8% CO_2) prior to the start of the experiments.
9
10
11 Neonatal normal human dermal fibroblasts (NHDF; CC-2509, Lonza, Basel, Switzerland)
12
13 were used as a reference cell culture as they have been frequently used in similar studies.
14
15
16
17 NHDFs were cultivated under the same conditions as clubfoot cells in the same culture
18
19
20 medium that contained 10 % FBS.
21

22 The cells for the experiments were seeded in polystyrene cell culture well plates (TPP,
23
24 Techno Plastic Products, Switzerland) or into glass bottom black cell culture 24 well plates
25
26 (P24-1.5H-N, Cellvis, Mountain View, CA, USA) suitable for microscopy imaging. Cell
27
28 seeding density of 10,000 cells/ cm^2 or 20,000 cells/ cm^2 was used, depending on the type of
29
30
31
32
33 experiment. Seeding density of 10,000 cell/ cm^2 was used when we preferred to evaluate the
34
35 proliferation of cells in different environments (initial MMC experiments, resazurin assay).
36
37
38 Seeding density of 20,000 cells/ cm^2 was used for gene expression, and second-harmonic
39
40 generation (SHG) microscopy, and experiments were used to measure ECM production. Cell
41
42 number and viability was determined by the Vi-CELL XR Analyzer (Beckman Coulter,
43
44 USA). After 24 hours, the cell culture medium was replaced with the medium supplemented
45
46 with 10% FBS, 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ Asc-2P, with/without the addition of MMC and with/without MXD.
47
48
49 The addition of MXD was considered as the start day (day 0) of treatment for all experiments.
50
51
52
53 The duration of the experiments ranged from 4 to 16 days, and is specified in the respective
54
55
56 method section. The cell culture media were changed every 3 to 4 days. The experiments with
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 MXD were conducted only with the selected MMC media group (Fc18) and with cells from
4
5
6 the contracted medial side (CF-M).
7

8 The cell seeding densities and the cultivation conditions for the experiments in the ECIS
9
10 real-time analysis system differ from all other experiments. We described them in detail in the
11
12 appropriate method section.
13
14

15 16 **Proliferation and cytotoxicity assays**

17
18 Detailed experimental procedure of cell mitochondrial activity measurement (resazurin
19
20 assay), ECIS (real-time, label-free cellular analysis) measurement and PicoGreen dsDNA
21
22 assay are described in Supporting Information Section 2.
23
24
25

26 27 **Immunofluorescence staining and microscopy**

28
29 Extracellular deposition of type I collagen was detected by immunofluorescence staining on
30
31 day 7 after seeding the cells into 24-well glass bottom black cell culture plates (P24-1.5H-N,
32
33 Cellvis, Mountain View, CA, USA). Cells were rinsed with phosphate-buffered saline
34
35 solution (PBS) with 5% FBS and were kept on ice. Then, a primary rabbit polyclonal
36
37 anti-collagen type I antibody (1:1000 in PBS with 5% FBS; LSL-LB-1197, Cosmo Bio,
38
39 Japan) was added for 2 hour incubation on ice, protected from light. Subsequently, the cells
40
41 were rinsed again with PBS with 5% FBS, were removed from the ice, and were fixed with
42
43 2% paraformaldehyde in PBS solution with 5% FBS for 20 minutes. The cells were again
44
45 rinsed with PBS and were incubated in PBS with 1% FBS for another 20 minutes to ensure
46
47 blocking of nonspecific binding sites. After washing with PBS, a secondary antibody Alexa
48
49 Fluor 488-conjugated F(ab')₂-Goat anti-Rabbit IgG (1:400 in PBS with 1% FBS; A-11070,
50
51 Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) was added for 1 hour at room temperature
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 together with Hoechst #33258 (5 µg/ml in PBS; 94403, Sigma-Aldrich, USA), which
4
5 penetrates through the non-permeabilised cell membrane to stain the cell nuclei. The
6
7 fluorescence signal was visualised by an Olympus IX51 epifluorescence microscope with a
8
9 DP74 camera (both Olympus Corp., Japan). The image acquisition settings were kept
10
11 identical for all wells.
12
13
14

15 16 **Analysis of fluorescence images**

17
18 Microphotographs obtained from the microscope (at least 10 per well, in triplicate) were
19
20 analysed using ImageJ FIJI software⁵⁴ (v.1.54f). Differences in the fluorescence signal of type
21
22 I collagen were measured after automatic background subtraction as an integrated
23
24 fluorescence density in the entire image area. The amount of deposited type I collagen was
25
26 expressed as the integrated fluorescence density value (IntDen), normalised to the mean value
27
28 measured in the Ctrl wells (non-treated cells cultivated in media without MMC). The number
29
30 of cells in each image was determined from the staining of the nuclei, which were counted
31
32 automatically using the ImageJ FIJI StarDist plugin.⁵⁵
33
34
35
36
37
38

39 **Second-harmonic generation imaging**

40
41 Cells for second-harmonic generation (SHG) imaging were seeded in 24-well glass bottom
42
43 black cell culture plates (P24-1.5H-N, Cellvis, Mountain View, CA, USA) and were analysed
44
45 on day 7 of cultivation in MMC media. The cells were kept alive for the imaging, as this
46
47 method is label-free, and fixation would reduce the SHG signal. The SHG signal was obtained
48
49 on a confocal microscope in order to determine the presence of properly structured type I
50
51 collagen fibers. Cells in the glass bottom well plate were visualised using a 63x water
52
53 immersion objective (HC PL APO CS 2 63x/1.20 Water), mounted on a Leica DMI8 inverted
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 microscope with a Leica TCS SP8 X confocal unit (Leica Microsystems, Germany). A
4
5 Chameleon Discovery TPC pulsed femtosecond laser (Coherent Inc., USA; 860 nm tunable
6
7 output, 80 Mhz, 1.6 W) was used to generate SHG (green pseudocolour) and autofluorescence
8
9 (red pseudocolour) signals. Leica non-descanned HyD detectors and a 430/24 band-pass filter
10
11 were used for collecting the SHG signals, and Leica non-descanned HyD detectors and a
12
13 610/75 band-pass filter were used for collecting the autofluorescence signals.
14
15
16
17

18 **Sircol assay**

19
20
21 To analyse the pattern of collagen deposition in cell culture under MMC (Fc18) conditions,
22
23 different sample fractions were extracted (media fraction, pepsin/acid-soluble ECM fraction,
24
25 and cross-linked insoluble ECM fraction). The cells were grown in 6-well polystyrene plates
26
27 for 16 days to ensure a sufficient amount of cell-deposited ECM for the analysis. Low protein
28
29 binding collection tubes (90410, 1.5 ml, Thermo Scientific, USA) were used for handling
30
31 samples throughout the experiment to minimise loss of the material. The Sircol Soluble
32
33 Collagen Assay Kit (S1000, BioVendor, UK) was used to analyse the collagen content in the
34
35 media fraction and in the pepsin/acid-soluble ECM fraction of the samples.
36
37
38
39
40
41

42 The fraction of soluble collagen deposited in the media was measured in the media
43
44 conditioned by the cells cultured with/without MMC (Fc18) for at least 4 days after the last
45
46 media change until the end of the experiment. 1 mL of conditioned media per sample was
47
48 used for analysis, together with a fresh sample of the corresponding media type as a blank.
49
50 The analysis procedure was the same as for samples from the pepsin/acid-soluble collagen
51
52 fraction (described below), with the omission of the pepsin digestion step. Fresh media from
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 each group were used as blanks to account for any interference of non-collagenous proteins
4
5 (e.g. from serum).⁵⁶
6
7

8 The fraction of pepsin/acid-soluble collagen in ECM was extracted and analysed as follows:
9
10 Cell layers were rinsed with PBS. Collagen was recovered from the cell layers by acidic
11
12 pepsin digestion (0.1 mg/ml in 0.5 M acetic acid; pepsin EC 3.4.23.1. from Sigma-Aldrich,
13
14 USA) in a cold room, on a shaker. After overnight incubation, the cell layers were harvested
15
16 with a cell scraper, transferred to low protein binding tubes and centrifuged. The pepsin
17
18 insoluble pellet was stored at 4°C for later use, while the supernatant was used to continue the
19
20 soluble Sircol assay according to the kit manufacturer protocol. The amount of collagen in the
21
22 samples was then determined from the standard curve based on the binding of Sirius Red dye
23
24 and was normalised to the untreated control samples (Ctrl).
25
26
27
28
29
30

31 The pellets of the insoluble collagen fraction from each sample were analysed with the
32
33 Hydroxyproline assay, as well as a parallel set of samples for the detection of total collagen
34
35 content.
36
37
38

39 **Hydroxyproline assay**

40
41 Cells were washed with PBS, lysed in RIPA buffer (R0278, Sigma-Aldrich, USA),
42
43 harvested with a cell scraper and collected into heat-resistant polypropylene screw cap tubes.
44
45 After sonication, an aliquot of each sample was used to perform a Pierce BCA assay (23225,
46
47 ThermoFisher Scientific, USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions to measure the
48
49 total protein content in the sample.
50
51
52
53

54 The rest of each sample was then digested in 6N HCl at 120°C for 3 hours. The amount of
55
56 collagen deposited in the extracellular matrix was determined as the hydroxyproline content
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 in the sample, using the Hydroxyproline Colorimetric Assay Kit (MAK008, Sigma-Aldrich,
4 USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Both assays were measured using a
5
6 VersaMax Absorbance Microplate Reader (Molecular Devices, USA) at 560 nm. The amount
7
8 of hydroxyproline is customarily used to calculate the total collagen content in cell culture or
9
10 tissue samples, which can be extrapolated by multiplying the sample hydroxyproline by a
11
12 factor of 6.6.⁵⁷
13
14
15
16
17

18
19 In the experiments with MXD, the cells were grown at the same density, but in 12-well
20
21 plates. A whole sample was analysed, representing both intracellular collagen and collagen
22
23 deposited in the extracellular matrix layer. Thus the relative configuration of hydroxyproline
24
25 is normalised to the total protein content per sample. In experiments to determine the total
26
27 amount of insoluble collagen in the corresponding sample fraction, the total protein content
28
29 could not be measured. The data are therefore presented as the relative concentration of
30
31 hydroxyproline.
32
33
34
35

36 **Enzyme-linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA)**

37
38
39 The concentration of pyridinoline and deoxypyridinoline cross-links in the cell-produced
40
41 extracellular matrix of samples with/without MXD treatment was measured by ELISA, using
42
43 the MicroVue PYD Enzyme Immunoassay kit (8010, MicroVue Quidel, San Diego, CA,
44
45 USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Aliquots of samples previously analysed
46
47 by the hydroxyproline assay were used for these measurements. The concentration of the
48
49 cross-links was normalised to the concentration of hydroxyproline and total protein in the
50
51 same sample.
52
53
54
55

56 **RNA isolation and Real-Time PCR**

1
2
3 Real-time PCR was performed to assess differences in the relative expression of mRNA of
4 selected genes. After 24 hours of cultivation with/without MMC (Fc18) and MXD treatment,
5
6 the cell RNA was isolated using the Total RNA Purification Micro Kit Plus (48500, Norgen
7
8 Biotek, Canada). A NanoDrop One^c microvolume UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Thermo
9
10 Scientific, USA) was used to check RNA quality and quantity. RNA at a concentration
11
12 of 300ng/μl was used for reverse transcription into cDNA by the Omniscript Reverse
13
14 Transcription Kit (205113, Qiagen, Germany) with a Random Primer Mix (S1330S, New
15
16 England BioLabs, USA). The reaction was performed in a T-Personal Thermocycler
17
18 (Biometra, Germany).

19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26 Real-time PCR was performed using 5xHOT FIREPol Probe qPCR Mix Plus (ROX)
27
28 (08-14-00008, Solis BioDyne, Estonia) and TaqMan Gene Expression Assays (Life
29
30 Technologies, USA) labelled with the FAM reporter dye specific to target the following
31
32 human genes: the extracellular matrix proteins collagen type I alpha-1 chain (*COL1A1*;
33
34 Hs00164004_m1), collagen type I alpha-2 chain (*COL1A2*; Hs00164099_m1), collagen type
35
36 III alpha-1 chain (*COL3A1*; Hs00943809_m1), collagen type VI alpha-3 chain (*COL6A3*;
37
38 Hs0091523_m1), and fibronectin 1 (*FNI*; Hs01549976_m1), the enzymes catalysing collagen
39
40 post-translational modifications lysyl hydroxylase 1 (*PLOD1*; Hs00386343_m1), lysyl
41
42 hydroxylase 2 (*PLOD2*; Hs01118184_m1), lysyl hydroxylase 3 (*PLOD3*; Hs01126612_m1),
43
44 lysyl oxidase (*LOX*; Hs00942483_m1), and prolyl 4-hydroxylase (*P4HDM*;
45
46 Hs00977922_m1), the pro-fibrotic cytokine transforming growth factor beta-1 (*TGFBI*;
47
48 Hs00998133_m1), the cytoskeletal protein alpha-smooth muscle actin (*ACTA2*;
49
50 Hs00909449_m1), the collagen degradation enzymes matrix metalloproteinase 2 and 9
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 (*MMP2*, *MMP9*, Hs01548727_m1, Hs00957562_m1), and a reference gene beta-actin
4
5
6 (*ACTB*; Hs99999903_m1).
7

8 The final reaction was conducted using the LightCycler 480 Instrument (Roche,
9 Switzerland). The total reaction volume was 20 μ l, and the cycle parameters were as follows:
10
11 2 min at 50°C, 10 min at 95°C, 40 cycles of 15 sec at 95°C and 1 min at 60°C. The results are
12
13 presented as $2^{(-\Delta\Delta Ct)}$. Data were normalised against a reference gene and according to the
14
15 gene expression in the untreated control sample (Ctrl).
16
17
18
19
20
21
22

23 **Immunohistochemical staining**

24
25 The data presented here complement our previously published data in the study by Novotny
26
27 *et al.*¹⁹, and are used together to discuss points raised in this study. The immunohistochemistry
28
29 staining was performed on the same set of patients' tissues as in the study mentioned above
30
31 and with the same methods. Briefly, tissue samples from the medial side (M-side) and the
32
33 lateral side (L-side) of 10 patients with relapsed clubfoot were fixed and embedded in
34
35 paraffin. Primary antibodies anti-collagen III (C7805, Sigma; 1:500, 1 hour at room
36
37 temperature), anti-collagen VI (ab6588, Abcam; 1:200, 30 min at room temperature), anti-
38
39 LH1 (ab262947, Abcam; 1:100, 1 hour at room temperature), anti-Lhx2/LH2 [CL6137]
40
41 (ab243030, Abcam; 1:500, 1 hour at room temperature), anti-PLOD3 (LH3) (ab128698,
42
43 Abcam; 1:400, overnight at 4°C) were used for detection by immunohistochemistry (IHC).
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51 Antigen retrieval, hydrogen peroxide block, protein block, secondary antibody reaction, and
52
53 visualisation were performed according to the Abcam protocol by applying the EXPOSE
54
55 Mouse and Rabbit Specific HRP/DAB IHC Detection Kit (ab236466, Abcam, Cambridge,
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 UK). The slides were counterstained with hematoxylin. The positivity of the detected
4
5 antibodies was evaluated using a light microscope, and was subsequently quantified with
6
7 image analyser signal thresholding in the NIS Elements 3.0 AR program (Laboratory
8
9 Imaging, Czech Republic). The number of pixels within the signal range was quantified from
10
11 10 independent areas of each sample and was used to calculate the mean percentage of the
12
13 positive area in each sample. Mean percentage values for each patient are presented in scatter
14
15 plots and were statistically compared across the experimental groups with a paired t-test.
16
17
18
19

20 21 **Statistical analysis**

22
23 SigmaStat 4.0 (Systat Software Inc., USA) or GraphPad Prism 10 (GraphPad Software,
24
25 USA) was used to check normality and variance (homoscedasticity) of the data and to
26
27 perform statistical analyses. A parametric statistical test with an appropriate post-hoc test (i.e.
28
29 Paired t-test, One-Way ANOVA with Dunnet's or Tukey's test for multiple comparisons,
30
31 Unpaired t-test with Welch's correction) were used if conditions for normality and equal
32
33 variance of data were met. If these assumptions were violated, a non-parametric test was used
34
35 (i.e. a Kruskal-Wallis test with Dunn's multiple comparisons test). Two-Way ANOVA with
36
37 Tukey's test for multiple comparisons was used to analyse the data from experiments
38
39 with/without an MMC environment and minoxidil, when applicable. Significance of the
40
41 differences was set at $p < 0.05$ unless stated otherwise. Formats in which the data are
42
43 presented are specified in the respective figure captions along with the statistical tests that
44
45 were used. All graphs were created in GraphPad Prism.
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53

54 **Results**

1
2
3 **MMC controls cell proliferation and metabolic activity depending on MMC concentration**
4
5
6 **and cell type sensitivity**
7

8 First, we investigated the effect of Ficoll 70 kDa + Ficoll 400 kDa mix (Fc) and
9 Polyvinylpyrrolidone 40 kDa (PVP) in a range of concentrations (Fc 4-54, PVP 9-54% FVO
10 v/v in the media) on all three cell types. We seeded primary cell cultures of clubfoot-derived
11 fibroblasts from the fibrotic contracted tissue of relapsed patients (CF-M) and from non-
12 contracted clubfoot tissue from the opposite side of the foot (CF-L) in parallel with normal
13 human dermal fibroblasts (NHDFs). We observed the native state of the cells on day 4 and
14 their metabolic activity (viability) on day 4, 7 and 11. The detailed analysis and results are
15 described in Supporting Information Section 3.1, Figure S1. We quantified the number of cell
16 nuclei in samples on day 7 (Figure 1A, Figure 2A, Figure 3A).
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30

31 All three cell types proliferated well in both tested MMC agents up to 18% FVO. However,
32 concentrations of 36% FVO (Fc36, PVP36) and especially 54% FVO (Fc54, PVP54)
33 appeared to inhibit the proliferation of all cell types. This inhibition was stronger for NHDFs
34 and CF-L cells, where both the proliferation and the viability of cells grown in PVP36 and
35 PVP54 were relatively low. The cell density on day 7 was in accordance with the metabolic
36 activity of CF-M cells in these MMC concentrations (Figure S1B). Interestingly, on day 7, the
37 Fc at 4-18% FVO significantly enhanced the proliferation of NHDF, but only Fc at 18%
38 significantly increased the proliferation in CF-L and CF-M cells (Figure 1A, Figure 2A,
39 Figure 3A).
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Figure 1. Proliferation and extracellular type I collagen deposition of NHDF fibroblasts after 7 days of culture with/without MMC. **(A)** Cell proliferation in media with different MMC concentrations. Truncated violin plot, median with IQR (n=18-137). Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA, Dunn's test (vs. Ctrl). **(B)** Integrated fluorescence density of extracellular collagen relative to Ctrl (no MMC). Mean + SEM (n=5-6). Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA, Dunn's test (vs. Ctrl). **(C)** Demonstrative images of extracellular type I collagen deposition after fluorescent staining. Olympus IX51 microscope, 10× objective. Scale bar = 200 μm.

Figure 2. Proliferation and extracellular type I collagen deposition of non-contracted clubfoot-derived cells (CF-L) after 7 days of culture with/without MMC. **(A)** Cell proliferation in media with different MMC concentrations. Truncated violin plot, Median with IQR (n=10-54). Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA, Dunn's test (vs. Ctrl). **(B)** Integrated fluorescence density of extracellular collagen relative to Ctrl (without MMC). Mean + SEM (n=5-6). Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA, Dunn's test (vs. Ctrl). **(C)** Demonstrative images of extracellular type I collagen deposition after fluorescent staining. Olympus IX51 microscope, 10× objective. Scale bar = 200 μm.

Figure 3. Proliferation and extracellular type I collagen deposition of contracted **clubfoot-derived cells (CF-M)** after 7 days of culture with/without MMC. **(A)** Cell proliferation in media with different MMC concentrations. Truncated violin plot, median with IQR (n=24-75). Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA, Dunn's test (vs. Ctrl). **(B)** Integrated fluorescence density of extracellular collagen relative to Ctrl (without MMC). Mean + SEM (n=5-7). Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA, Dunn's test (vs. Ctrl). **(C)** Demonstrative images of extracellular type I collagen deposition after fluorescent staining. Olympus IX51 microscope, 10× objective. Scale bar = 200 μm.

1
2
3 **MMC enhanced collagen deposition and collagen supramolecular assembly in the cultures**
4 **of clubfoot-derived and NHDF fibroblasts**
5
6
7

8 We compared collagen production by cells grown under MMC conditions by fluorescent
9 staining of type I collagen deposited in the extracellular matrix after 6 days of treatment (7
10 days in total). We observed slight to significant increases of collagen in both MMC media
11 types (Fc, PVP) and concentrations across all cell types with the exception of PVP54, in
12 which we could see a minimal amount of extracellular collagen (Figure 1, Figure 2, Figure 3
13 B and C). Most likely, this could be attributed to the lowest number of viable cells growing in
14 PVP54 wells. The collagen deposited by cells in PVP54 appeared to be in a more granulated
15 form rather than in a fibrillar form, which also often seemed to be the case with Fc54, and to
16 some extent with Fc36. In general, our observation can be correlated with the relatively low
17 density of cells in particular optical fields. In contrast, we detected the highest extracellular
18 collagen production in Fc18 in all cell types, with Fc9 as the second highest in two of them
19 (Figure 1, Figure 2, Figure 3 B and C). We compared the relative integrated fluorescence
20 density (IntDen) of extracellular collagen from fluorescence microphotographs of the cells
21 cultivated with MMC and the control cells in a standard medium (Ctrl=1). NHDF cells in
22 Fc18 had the highest relative collagen production (value of 4.24). It was lower in CF-L (Fc18)
23 (value of 3.73) and lowest in CF-M (Fc18) (value of 2.40). We also detected a significant
24 increase in collagen production in Fc9, where NHDF (Fc9) reached a value of 2.96 and CF-M
25 (Fc9) reached a value of 2.01 relative to Ctrl. NHDFs was the only cell type in which we
26 detected a significant increase in collagen deposition in PVP18, which was 3.00 relative to
27 Ctrl (Figure 1, Figure 2, Figure 3 B). Although the choice of the best macromolecular crowder
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 to promote ECM deposition appears to be cell-specific to some extent, our findings are
4
5 consistent with the frequent use of 18% FVO crowding concentration in other studies with
6
7 fibroblasts.^{31,33,38,42,43}
8
9

10
11 To further examine collagen deposition, we imaged live cells grown in the same
12
13 experimental setup with label-free confocal microscopy visualising the SHG signal of
14
15 collagen fibers. SHG offers qualitative information about collagen supramolecular assembly,
16
17 which was indeed reported to be accelerated in MMC conditions.⁵⁸ The SHG signal revealed
18
19 that in just a 7 day experiment the Fc18 media accelerated structural maturation and the
20
21 assembly of collagen fibers in all cell types to a detectable level (Figure 4). According to our
22
23 experience, a strong SHG signal can usually be detected in a fibroblast cell culture after 3
24
25 weeks of cultivation,^{22,59} a time which was significantly shortened to a week with the use of
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
MMC in a cell culture.

Figure 4. Maturation of collagen fibers. SHG imaging of type I collagen fibers after 7 days of cultivation of normal human fibroblasts (NHDFs) and clubfoot-derived fibroblasts (CF-L, CF-M) with (Fc9, Fc18, PVP18) or without (Ctrl) macromolecularly crowded media - demonstrative images. The red signal (upper row) is the autofluorescence of cells. The green signal (lower row) is SHG. Leica DMI8 inverted microscope with a Leica TCS SP8 X confocal unit, 63× water immersion objective. Scale bar = 50 μm .

The three tested cell types (NHDFs healthy fibroblast control, clubfoot non-contracted control CF-L, and CF-M from fibrotic clubfoot tissue) exhibited similar behaviour under

1
2
3 MMC conditions. We therefore continued the experiments only with the Fc18 media, which
4
5 was the best-performing MMC combination, and with CF-M cells to explore the
6
7 advantageous effect of the MMC microenvironment in the development of an *in vitro* model
8
9 of clubfoot fibrosis.
10
11

12
13 **MMC (Fc18) supported higher conversion of soluble collagen into insoluble collagen in the**
14
15 **culture of clubfoot-derived fibroblasts**
16
17

18
19 Some limitations to the use of primary patient's cells in clubfoot research are the relative
20
21 scarcity of samples and limited access to large amounts of cells of low passages. The higher
22
23 mean population doubling time of CF-M (approx. 30 hours²²) in comparison to NHDFs
24
25 (approx. 24 hours) and CF-L (approx. 27 hours, data not shown) in standard cultivation
26
27 conditions also adds to the prospect of longer cultivation times to generate enough
28
29 extracellular matrix for specific analyses. To quantify the stages of collagen production and
30
31 incorporation into the extracellular matrix, we cultivated CF-M with and without Fc18 for 16
32
33 days. Subsequently, we measured the amount of collagen in distinct fractions of a sample
34
35 using Sircol and Hydroxyproline assays. The microenvironment created by modifying the
36
37 culture medium with MMC promoted the conversion of soluble collagen towards non-soluble
38
39 collagen and accelerated its deposition into the extracellular matrix. The amount of soluble
40
41 collagen measured in the culture medium was 3.7 times lower in Fc18 than in Ctrl (Figure
42
43 5A). Collagen newly deposited into the extracellular matrix and recently cross-linked collagen
44
45 (soluble in pepsin and acetic acid solution) was 2.3 times lower in the Fc18 group (Figure
46
47 5B). In contrast, the amount of cross-linked, insoluble collagen deposited into the cellular
48
49 layer was 2.0-fold higher in Fc18 (Figure 5C). The total amount of collagen deposited into the
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

cell layer after 16 days of cultivation was 1.5-fold higher in the Fc18 group than in Ctrl (Figure 5D).

Figure 5. Analysis of collagen deposition by clubfoot-derived fibroblasts (CF-M) in distinct fractions of the sample during 16-day cultivation without (Ctrl) or with (Fc18) macromolecularly crowded media. **(A)** Collagen produced into cultivation media between media changes (n=6). **(B)** Soluble collagen newly deposited into the extracellular matrix of the cell layer (n=9). **(C)** Insoluble cross-linked collagen deposited into the extracellular matrix (n=11). **(D)** Total collagen deposited in the cell layer extracellular matrix (n=14). Scatter plots, Median with 95% CI. Paired t-test (****p<0.0001).

MMC (Fc18) stimulated the expression of fibrosis-related genes in clubfoot-derived fibroblasts

At the mRNA level, clubfoot cells reacted to the addition of Fc18 media as early as 4 hours after the media change with a slight but insignificant increase in gene expression (data not shown). However, after 24 hours (Figure 6), the levels had risen significantly for genes *PLOD2*, *PLOD3* (encoding lysyl hydroxylase 2 and 3 - the enzymes catalysing collagen post-

translational modifications and cross-linking), *FNI* (fibronectin 1, i.e. an extracellular matrix protein), *TGFB1* (transforming growth factor beta-1, i.e. a pro-fibrotic cytokine), *ACTA2* (alpha-smooth muscle actin, i.e. a cytoskeletal protein, marker of myofibroblast formation), and also *COL6A3* (collagen type VI alpha 3 chain), *MMP2* and *MMP9* (matrix metalloproteinases 2 and 9 - collagen degradation enzymes). By contrast, the expression of genes for other tested extracellular matrix proteins such as procollagen structural components *COL1A1*, *COL1A2* (collagen type I alpha-1 and alpha-2 chains), *COL3A1* (collagen type III alpha-1 chain), and other collagen modifying enzymes *PLOD1* (lysyl hydroxylase 1), *LOX* (lysyl oxidase) and *P4THM* (prolyl 4-hydroxylase) remained unchanged or exhibited large variance both in Ctrl and in the Fc18 medium. No significant decrease in gene expression of the measured markers was detected in Fc18. These results indicate that MMC, specifically in Fc18 form, shifts CF-M fibroblasts towards pro-fibrotic phenotype without any other supplementation.

Figure 6. Relative mRNA expression of genes in clubfoot-derived fibroblasts (CF-M) after 24 hours of cultivation without (Ctrl) or with (Fc18) a macromolecularly crowded environment. Genes of interest: *COL1A1*, *COL1A2* (collagen type I alpha-1 and alpha-2 chains); *COL3A1*

1
2
3 (collagen type III alpha-1 chain); *COL6A3* (collagen type VI alpha-3 chain); *PLOD1*,
4
5
6 *PLOD2*, *PLOD3* (lysyl hydroxylase 1, 2 and 3); *LOX* (lysyl oxidase); P4THM (prolyl-4-
7
8 hydroxylase); *FNI* (fibronectin 1); *TGFB1* (transforming growth factor-beta 1); *ACTA2*
9
10 (alpha-smooth muscle actin); *MMP2*, *MMP9* (matrix metalloproteinases 2 and 9). Normalised
11
12 against *ACTB* (beta-actin) reference gene. Data presented as $2^{-(\Delta\Delta Ct)}$, relative to Ctrl
13
14 (calibrator). Mean + SD (n=3-5). Unpaired t-test with Welch's correction (*p < 0.05, **p <
15
16 0.01, ***p < 0.001).

21
22
23
24 Interestingly, these results correlated well with previously published analyses of clubfoot
25
26 tissues in our earlier studies.^{17,19} We performed new complementary immunohistochemistry
27
28 (IHC) analyses of additional markers on the paraffin-embedded tissue sections previously
29
30 collected for the study by Novotny *et al.*¹⁹ to provide more comprehensive information for
31
32 comparison with our *in vitro* model. IHC staining against collagen type III, collagen type VI,
33
34 and collagen-cross-linking enzymes lysyl hydroxylase 2 and 3 (LH2, LH3) showed a
35
36 significantly increased area of tissue sections positively stained for these antigens in samples
37
38 of contracted medial side clubfoot tissue when compared to the lateral side tissue (Figure 7).
39
40 Significant extracellular IHC positivity was detected for both collagen types III and VI,
41
42 whereas nuclear and cytosolic positivity was detected for LH2, and only nuclear positivity in
43
44 the case of LH3. Lysyl hydroxylase 1 (LH1) was not detected in the tissues from either side.
45
46 Related IHC data regarding upregulation in TGF-beta 1, alpha-smooth muscle actin,
47
48 fibronectin, LOX, MMP2, MMP9 in clubfoot medial tissue were published in Novotny *et*
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 *al.*¹⁹ and data for type I collagen were published in Knitlova *et al.*¹⁸ We therefore refer to
4
5
6 them in more detail in the discussion.
7

1
2
3 **Figure 7.** Comparison of contracted (M-side) and non-contracted (L-side) of clubfoot tissue -
4
5 complementary data. **(A)** Demonstrative images of immunohistochemical (IHC) staining and
6
7 signal detection. Staining of collagen type III and VI, lysyl hydroxylases 1, 2 and 3 (LH1,
8
9 LH2, LH3). The red areas in the ST (signal threshold) columns represent the positive pixels
10
11 after thresholding. An image analyser was then used to measure the percentage of the area
12
13 with a positive signal from the total area. *E+* Extracellular positivity, *N+* Nuclear positivity,
14
15 *C+* Cytosolic positivity, *N/A* Not Assessed. Scale bar = 20 μm . **(B)** The percentage of COL3,
16
17 COL6, LH2 and LH3 positive area after IHC signal quantification. LH1 was not detectable.
18
19 Scatter plots, median with 95% CI (n=10). Paired t-test (**p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001).
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29

30 **MMC (Fc18) positively influenced the proliferation of clubfoot-derived fibroblasts in the**
31
32 **presence of minoxidil**

33
34
35 In our earlier experiments, we have already determined the MXD concentrations suitable
36
37 for standard cell culture of clubfoot-derived cells.²² Here, we aimed to explore if the dose-
38
39 dependent inhibitory effect of minoxidil on cell proliferation that we had previously observed
40
41 follows the same trend when administered in Fc18 media. We generally observed a
42
43 moderately positive effect on cell proliferation in MMC medium Fc18. We therefore tested a
44
45 full range of MXD concentrations again, including the highest concentrations, with CF-M
46
47 cells seeded at a density of 10,000 per cm^2 .
48
49
50
51
52

53 We monitored the effect of the absence or presence of MXD in concentrations of 0, 0.25,
54
55 0.50, 0.75, 1, and 2 mM on clubfoot-derived cells in Ctrl and Fc18 media in real-time for 160
56
57 hours using the Electric Cell-substrate Impedance Sensing device (ECIS) (Figure S2A).
58
59
60

1
2
3 Subsequently, we estimated the amount of cellular dsDNA in the samples (Figure S2B). The
4
5 results are described in detail in the Supporting Information Section 3.2. We confirmed that
6
7 generally larger amounts of cells are growing in the Fc18 media, i.e. about 30% more than in
8
9 the Ctrl media in all MXD groups, except for the highest concentration. Based on these
10
11 analyses, we excluded 1 and 2 mM MXD from further analysis, due to their strong inhibitory
12
13 effect on cell proliferation.
14
15
16
17

18
19 **The reduction of collagen production, deposition and cross-linking by minoxidil treatment**
20
21 **was less pronounced in MMC (Fc18)**
22
23

24 With a focus on ECM deposition, we performed the rest of the experiments with CF-M cells
25
26 seeded at a density of 20,000 per cm². Higher initial cell density practically erased the
27
28 difference between the cell proliferation rates in the Ctrl and Fc18 media on day 7, when no
29
30 MXD or a low concentration of 0.25 mM MXD was added (Figure 8). We observed a notable
31
32 difference in a group with 0.75 mM MXD, in which case the cells in Fc18 media proliferated
33
34 faster by approximately 10% (Figure 8). At these conditions, the deposition of extracellular
35
36 type I collagen per cell under MXD treatment in the Ctrl media followed the same dose-
37
38 dependent decrease as previously reported.²² An analysis of microphotographs from
39
40 fluorescence microscopy showed that the Fc18 medium increased the total amount of collagen
41
42 deposited in all groups. However, the proportional differences between individual MXD
43
44 concentrations and the control without MXD are lower in the Fc18 medium compared to the
45
46 same concentrations in the Ctrl medium. The amount of deposited extracellular collagen in
47
48 the Ctrl group was reduced to 54%, 28% and 15% by the addition of 0.25, 0.5 and 0.75 mM
49
50 MXD, respectively. In the Fc18 group, the respective reductions were to 68%, 49% and 43%
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

relative to the non-treated samples (Figure 8C). A comparison between the collagen production after 7 days in Fc18 and the production measured in a standard cell culture after 21 days in Knitlova *et al.*²² suggests that the environment created by the Fc18 media enhanced and speeded up collagen deposition. The proportional amount of collagen that was deposited in Fc18 with higher MXD concentrations is closer to values observed at a later time intervals in standard cell culture.²² Both of the higher concentrations of MXD (0.5 and 0.75 mM) significantly reduced the collagen content.

Figure 8. Proliferation and extracellular collagen type I deposition of contracted clubfoot-derived cells (CF-M) after 7 days of culture without (Ctrl) or with (Fc18) macromolecularly crowded media and different concentrations of minoxidil (MXD). **(A)** Demonstrative images of extracellular type I collagen deposition (green) and cell density (blue - nuclei) after

1
2
3 fluorescent staining. Olympus IX51 microscope, 10× objective. Scale bar = 200 μm. **(B)** Cell
4 proliferation in Ctrl and Fc18 media with different MXD concentrations. Truncated violin
5 plot, Median with IQR (n=30-36). ANOVA, Tukey's test. **(C)** The amount of extracellular
6 collagen deposited presented as the integrated fluorescence density of extracellular type I
7 collagen normalised to the cell count. Box plot, Median with IQR (n=30-33). Kruskal-Wallis
8 ANOVA, Dunn's test (**p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001, ****p < 0.0001).

9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22 We measured the expression level of related genes to examine the effect of Fc18 media
23 with/without MXD on type I procollagen structural components and enzymes active in
24 collagen post-translational modifications. After 24 hours of treatment in both Fc18 and in
25 Ctrl, the expression of genes for lysyl hydroxylase isoforms 1, 2 and 3 (LH1, LH2, LH3;
26 encoded by genes *PLOD1*, *PLOD2*, *PLOD3*) were downregulated significantly and to a
27 similar extend by 0.5 and 0.75 mM MXD (Figure 9). The downregulation was slightly more
28 pronounced in the *PLOD1* and *PLOD3* expression in the Fc18 group, but we observed a more
29 significant decrease in *PLOD2* expression levels after MXD treatment in Fc18 than in the Ctrl
30 media. It was previously reported that the effect of minoxidil on specific lysyl hydroxylase
31 isoforms varies.⁶⁰ In clubfoot-derived cells, the relative expression of *PLOD1* was reduced the
32 most, followed by *PLOD3* and *PLOD2*. The genes for procollagen alpha chains (*COL1A1*,
33 *COL1A2*) were not significantly affected by the addition of MXD or by the type of medium.
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
The inhibitory effect of minoxidil on collagen is thus confirmed to be largely dependent on
the disruption of collagen fibrillogenesis in terms of downregulating the collagen cross-

linking enzyme expression, not via reduction of its precursors in the form of procollagen chains.

Figure 9. Relative mRNA expression of genes for collagen and collagen-crosslinking enzymes in clubfoot-derived fibroblasts (CF-M) after 24 hours of cultivation in non-crowded Ctrl or macromolecularly crowded Fc18 media with or without the addition of minoxidil (MXD). Genes of interest: *PLOD1*, *PLOD2*, *PLOD3* (lysyl hydroxylase 1, 2 and 3); *COL1A1*, *COL1A2* (collagen type I alpha-1 and alpha-2 chains). Normalised against *ACTB* (beta-actin) reference gene. Data presented as $2^{-(ddCt)}$, relative to Ctrl (calibrator). Mean + SD (n=4). Two-Way ANOVA, Tukey's multiple comparisons test (*p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001, ****p < 0.0001).

1
2
3 We then studied long-term collagen deposition and cross-linking after 16 days of cultivation
4 in Fc18/Ctrl media with or without MXD treatment. We measured the collagen concentration
5 and the cross-linking following the protocols supplied by kit manufacturers and we optimised
6 the procedures, as described in Capella-Monsonis *et al.*⁶¹ First, the total protein content in all
7 samples was estimated by a Pierce BCA assay, and then the hydroxyproline concentration
8 was measured in aliquots of the same samples. We extrapolated the amount of total collagen
9 by multiplying the hydroxyproline content by a factor of 6.6⁵⁷ and we normalised the values to
10 the protein content in the respective samples (Figure 10A). Then we measured the
11 concentration of pyridinoline and deoxypyridinoline trivalent cross-links in the samples, and
12 related it to the amount of collagen (Figure 10B). The total protein values reflected the trend
13 of MXD treatment, causing a reduction in all groups. Normalised collagen deposition was
14 higher in the Fc18 group, reaching a 1.43 times higher median value than in Ctrl (Figure
15 10A). However, the amount of total collagen per μg of protein in both groups treated with
16 MXD was very similar, with a more significant reduction in the Fc18 groups. The amount of
17 trivalent cross-links in the samples followed the same trend in general. The largest difference
18 between MXD-treated and non-treated groups were in cells grown in Fc18 media. Collagen
19 produced by cells grown in Fc18 without MXD was 1.18-times more cross-linked (Figure
20 10B), which is below statistical significance level. Nevertheless, the differences in the median
21 values were greater in the Fc18 group, which suggests that the joint effect of Fc18 and MXD
22 on collagen deposition and cross-linking in prolonged cell culture was greater than in the Ctrl
23 group.

Figure 10. Analysis of collagen matrix deposited by clubfoot-derived (CF-M) cells after 16 days of cultivation in non-crowded Ctrl or macromolecularly crowded Fc18 media with or without minoxidil (MXD) treatment. **(A)** Long-term collagen deposition was measured by hydroxyproline assay and was normalised to the total protein concentration in the sample. **(B)** The level of collagen cross-linking was measured as the concentration of pyridinoline and deoxypyridinoline cross-links and is presented relative to the concentration of collagen in the samples. Box plots, Median with IQR (n=6). Two-Way ANOVA, Tukey's multiple comparisons test (*p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001, ****p < 0.0001).

Discussion

The introduction of macromolecular crowding (MMC) in standard *in vitro* cell culture has been proven beneficial, and has been advocated in numerous studies for use in drug screening.^{25,33,37,62} MMC has found application in cancer research,⁶³ in studies of cell differentiation into various lineages,^{39,41} in modelling of fibrotic diseases and scarring,^{31,33,37,44} and for the development of ECM-rich cell-derived matrices^{24,35} and cell sheets.^{41,45} However,

1
2
3 MMC has never been used with clubfoot primary cells to model the fibrotic conditions of this
4
5 disease. We took this step to evaluate the effect of MMC on the production of ECM by
6
7 clubfoot fibroblasts and possibly to harness its benefits in research for clubfoot adjuvant
8
9 treatment. Firstly, with the addition of MMC, we aimed to create a pseudo-3D biomimetic *in*
10
11 *vitro* model of clubfoot fibrosis to set a basis for more effective anti-fibrotic drug testing.
12
13 Secondly, we envisioned combining MMC with a scaffold simulating the stiffness of the
14
15 original pathological tissue in the future to bring the model even closer to representing the *in*
16
17 *vivo* state (i.e. using decellularised clubfoot tissue slices or a decellularised matrix-derived
18
19 hydrogel prepared from these tissues). Our efforts focus on bridging the gap between standard
20
21 cell culture and animal models of idiopathic clubfoot.
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

29 The work with patient-derived cells is a basic limitation of this study, as primary cells tend
30
31 to lose their phenotype and, in our case, their pro-fibrotic characteristics during prolonged
32
33 cultivation. To avoid this, we used clubfoot-isolated cells within their first to third passage, as
34
35 determined by monitoring cell markers during passaging in our previous study.²² However,
36
37 some inter-patient variability in the primary cells is unavoidable. Furthermore, the
38
39 opportunities to access tissue samples from clubfoot are limited to post-relapse corrective
40
41 surgeries. Despite the relatively small number of patients included in our study, our set
42
43 reflected the male:female (2:1) incidence ratio of clubfoot with 5 male and 2 female donors.
44
45 Idiopathic clubfoot is defined as a disease of multifactorial origin with a possible polygenic
46
47 nature,⁴ but there is no data available suggesting that the patient's gender could have any
48
49 impact on the behaviour of isolated cells.
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 For MMC induction, we selected two different approaches to test: a) the mix of Ficoll 70
4 with Ficoll 400 (referred to as Fc) and b) Polyvinylpyrrolidone 40 (PVP), both of which
5
6 demonstrated promising results in recent studies with human fibroblasts.^{25,32,33,37,38,42} The ratio
7
8 of the Ficoll mix that we selected corresponds to the ratio most used in the referenced
9
10 literature. The range of concentrations that we used in our study to represent the fractional
11
12 volume occupancy (FVO) of the macromolecules in physiological environments (i.e. 4%, 9%,
13
14 18%, 36%, and 54% FVO) was inspired by these studies as well, most notably by the study of
15
16 Rashid *et al.*³⁸ This range follows previously calculated theoretical FVOs, which imitate
17
18 proteins in interstitial fluid (9% FVO), albumin in bone marrow (corresponds to 18%), blood
19
20 plasma (45%), and simulate the ECM environment (at 54% FVO). Increasing MMC
21
22 concentration in cell culture media resulted in a change in its viscosity. However, all of the
23
24 selected concentrations of both crowding agents were reported to fall within the viscosity of
25
26 human blood (except for the Fc mix at 54% FVO), with the Fc mix being generally more
27
28 viscous than PVP at all concentrations.³⁸

29
30
31 To facilitate the comparison of our results with the literature, we included normal human
32
33 dermal fibroblasts (NHDFs) in the initial tests, in addition to cells isolated from clubfoot
34
35 contracted fibrotic tissue (CF-M) and clubfoot non-contracted tissue (CF-L) from the other
36
37 side of the foot. The reason for including CF-L as an additional control cell type was the
38
39 inaccessibility of a more accurate clubfoot control, such as samples from healthy paediatric
40
41 patients or from patients after successful clubfoot therapy (non-relapsed). Samples from the
42
43 lateral side of the foot represent the most feasible option for observing the differences and
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 making comparisons with the contracted medial clubfoot tissue and, in relation, M/L-tissue-
4
5 derived cells.¹⁹
6
7

8 All cell types followed a similar trend in their proliferation and metabolic activity in
9
10 reaction to the tested concentrations of crowding agents (MMCs). In particular, both of our
11
12 control cell types (NHDFs, CF-L) exhibited a significant decrease (in Fc36, Fc54, PVP36) or
13
14 even cessation of proliferation (in PVP54), and reduction of metabolic activity when
15
16 cultivated in a highly crowded environment. This hindrance was presumably due to
17
18 overcrowding, which caused constrained diffusion of molecules in the media.⁶⁴ The effect was
19
20 stronger in PVP than in the Fc mix, likely because of the unequal sizes of the hydrodynamic
21
22 radii (R_H) of the molecules used for crowding (R_H : PVP 40 kDa = 5.1 nm; Fc 70 kDa = 4 nm,
23
24 Fc 400 kDa = 8 nm),^{58,65} and despite the fact that the reported viscosity of the Fc mix at 36%
25
26 and 54% FVO is higher than the viscosity of PVP alone.³⁸ The hydrodynamic radius
27
28 influences the volume that the macromolecule excludes from the solution and by extension
29
30 the diffusion speed of solutes. The difference in conformation of the crowding agents can also
31
32 play a role. Ficoll is near-spherical in the solution, while PVP adopts random, non-spherical
33
34 conformations.⁶⁶ The CF-M cells from the clubfoot fibrotic tissue were less prone to
35
36 overcrowding and they continued to proliferate, albeit more slowly. CF-M cell generally have
37
38 a longer doubling time, slower proliferation under MMC, and lower metabolic activity during
39
40 the early stage of the cell culture (day 4) compared to other tested cell types. Due to their
41
42 slower proliferation rate, these cells probably have lower metabolic requirements, which can
43
44 facilitate their survival even in highly crowded media. Despite the significant decrease in
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 proliferation, our cells did not die in the high FVO Ficoll mix, as did the fibroblasts in the
4
5 study of Rashid *et al.*³⁸
6
7

8 When investigating the deposition of extracellular collagen, we have observed an increase
9
10 in almost all MMC concentrations with all cell types. However, the CF-M cells again showed
11
12 to be less reactive, or rather the MMC did not elicit such a substantial difference in collagen
13
14 deposition from their untreated Ctrl as in other cell types. CF-L and NHDFs exhibited very
15
16 similar deposition profiles, with comparable extracellular collagen deposition levels in Fc4,
17
18 Fc9, Fc36, Fc54, PVP18 and PVP36, despite the different cell numbers. As previously
19
20 described, collagen produced in the cultivation environment continues to self-associate even
21
22 in cell-free systems, which is further promoted by MMC.²⁷ Thus, we can presume that the
23
24 collagen continued to assemble, but as a result, a rather granular form of deposition was
25
26 observed in groups where the viability of the cells was affected. A similar effect was seen
27
28 after 48 hours of rapid collagen deposition in cell culture with 500 kDa dextran sulfate at 5%
29
30 FVO by Chen *et al.*,²⁹ and also by Puerta Cavanzo *et al.*³³ after 96 hours in the same setup.
31
32 However, cell proliferation did not seem to be inhibited. The study of Rashid *et al.*,³⁸ who
33
34 were the only group who also compared high concentrations of Ficoll 70 and Ficoll 400
35
36 mixed crowding, did not report such a morphological difference in collagen deposited by
37
38 NHDFs at 36% or at 54% FVO.
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48

49 We observed the highest peak of MMC concentration efficacy to stimulate collagen
50
51 deposition in the Fc mix at 18% FVO, which resulted in approximately 4 times more collagen
52
53 than in the Ctrl groups of CF-L and NHDF cells. Meanwhile, in CF-M the mean difference
54
55 was only 2.4 times higher relative to Ctrl. The deposition by CF-M under other MMC
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 concentrations also expressed more variation from the trend seen with other cell types. We
4
5 speculate that this is due to CF-M naturally producing more collagen, which can contribute to
6
7 crowding of the media. The excluded volume effect of MMC, which increases procollagen
8
9 processing and collagen deposition, is not as pronounced in CF-M culture as in our control
10
11 cells. As a result, the difference between collagen deposited in Ctrl and MMC environments is
12
13 smaller. We did not compare the amount of collagen deposited by the three cell types
14
15 quantitatively at this point, because we were more interested in the overall differences in the
16
17 effect of MMC concentrations on clubfoot cells. Other studies consistently present 18% FVO
18
19 and sometimes 9% FVO of the Fc mix as the best-performing concentration of this crowding
20
21 agent for ECM deposition fibroblasts,^{29,33,38} which is in agreement with our results. We further
22
23 supported this conclusion with an analysis of the SHG signal. Among the MMC
24
25 concentrations that stimulated collagen deposition the best without negatively affecting cell
26
27 proliferation, we found that only Fc18 significantly accelerated the supramolecular assembly
28
29 of collagen fibers in all cell types. SHG signals of comparable strength were detected in the
30
31 culture of CF-M fibroblasts without MMC, usually after 3 weeks.²²

32
33
34 The standard long culture times eventually enable the cells to self-crowd the media and
35
36 deposit a comparable amount of collagen,³¹ which indicates that MMC is most effective in
37
38 early cell culture stages. Our analysis of collagen by fractions following the stages of its
39
40 biosynthesis⁶¹ showed that Fc18 also works efficiently during cell culture prolonged to 16
41
42 days. A significantly higher amount of collagen secreted by CF-M cells was found in the
43
44 media supernatant fraction in the Ctrl group. However, it should be noted that most of this
45
46 water-soluble collagen is taken away during media changes.⁵⁸ Recently deposited collagen in
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 the cell layer, represented by a fraction soluble by pepsin and acetic acid digestion, was also
4
5 higher in the Ctrl group. At the same time, the insoluble fraction, representing heavily cross-
6
7 linked collagen, prevailed by far in the Fc18 group, as did the total amount of deposited
8
9 collagen measured in the cell layer. Macromolecular crowding increases the relative density
10
11 of procollagen, as well as other peptides produced by the cells such as enzymes.³¹ Enzymes,
12
13 which are more readily available, can act before they are inactivated or their substrate is
14
15 dissolved. These enzymes include procollagen N- and C-proteinases, which cleave the
16
17 propeptide ends of the procollagen molecules, contributing to the decrease of their solubility
18
19 and initiating collagen fibril formation. The collagen crosslinking enzymes then stabilize the
20
21 collagen fiber. The conversion from soluble to insoluble collagen is, therefore, continuously
22
23 promoted by the MMC (Fc18) environment, even after 16 days in culture. Prolonged
24
25 cultivation in an MMC environment is useful for generating more ECM, measuring
26
27 biomarkers associated with ECM production over time, and modulating collagen cross-
28
29 linking.³⁷

30
31
32 As a final evaluation of the environment, we examined whether the change from standard
33
34 culture media to MMC media elicited changes in cellular gene expression. CF-M cells from
35
36 fibrotic clubfoot tissue showed an increase in fibrosis-associated markers under the influence
37
38 of an environment crowded with Fc18. After 24 hours of supplementation with Fc18 media,
39
40 the cells exhibited upregulated expression of genes encoding enzymes catalysing collagen
41
42 cross-linking - lysyl hydroxylases (LH2, LH3; genes *PLOD2*, *PLOD3*), pro-fibrotic cytokine
43
44 TGF-beta 1 (*TGFBI*), myofibroblast activation marker alpha-smooth muscle actin (*ACTA2*),
45
46 extracellular matrix protein fibronectin (*FNI*), type VI collagen (*COL6A3*), and matrix
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 metalloproteinases (*MMP2*, *MMP9*). There was no difference in the expression of genes for
4
5 other enzymes involved in the formation of collagen cross-links, e.g. lysyl oxidase (*LOX*) and
6
7 prolyl-4-hydroxylase (*P4THM*), or ECM proteins type I and III collagens (*COL1A1*,
8
9 *COL1A2*, *COL3A1*).

10
11
12
13
14 The expression profile induced in CF-M cells after cultivation in the MMC (Fc18)
15
16 environment shares a marked similarity with clubfoot fibrotic tissue. According to our
17
18 previous research,¹⁹ both histological staining and gene expression analysis of the fibrotic
19
20 medial side tissue revealed an increase in TGF-beta 1, alpha-smooth muscle actin, and
21
22 fibronectin. MMP2 and MMP9 were also upregulated in stained histological sections when
23
24 compared to the control tissue from the lateral side of clubfoot. At the same time, no increase
25
26 in gene expression of MMPs was detected. Clubfoot medial side tissue contained a higher
27
28 accumulation of ECM proteins collagen type I,¹⁸ type III and type VI than the control tissue,
29
30 which is in accordance with proteomic data in Eckhardt *et al.*¹⁷ Collagen-modifying enzymes
31
32 lysyl oxidase¹⁹ and lysyl hydroxylases (except LH1) were also upregulated in the tissues of
33
34 relapsed clubfoot. In relation to these data, the higher collagen content with a higher level of
35
36 trivalent pyridinium cross-links found in clubfoot fibrotic tissue has a direct impact through
37
38 its more difficult degradation,¹⁸ and influences its biomechanical characteristics such as a
39
40 higher Young's elastic modulus.²⁰

41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49 Although some changes may be tissue-specific, rich representation of ECM proteins like
50
51 collagens and fibronectin in fibrotic tissues and upregulation of markers such as TGF-beta,
52
53 alpha-smooth muscle actin, and increased cross-linking are commonly associated with
54
55 fibrogenesis. MMPs play a multifaceted role in fibrosis; they not only serve as a collagen-
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 degrading enzyme but are generally associated with cell differentiation, ECM maturation and
4 remodelling.⁶⁷ An increase in MMP2 and 9 activity as a function of enhanced ECM deposition
5
6 stimulated via an MMC environment with carrageenan was reported by Cigognini *et al.*³⁹
7
8
9

10
11 *In vitro* fibrotic models are often based on normal healthy cells with supplementation of
12 pro-fibrotic stimuli^{33,36,37} or on cells isolated from pathological tissues with pro-fibrotic
13 phenotype,^{18,22,49} cultivated in standard culture conditions,⁴⁹ in macromolecularly crowded
14 environments,^{33,36,37} or using a combination of these approaches. In these studies, the models
15 were used to screen various drugs with anti-fibrotic potential (i.e. pirfenidone, nintedanib,
16 omipalisib, minoxidil, BAPN and ALK5i). Research carried out by Puerta Cavanzo *et al.*³³
17 compared the gene expression of nonstimulated normal human dermal fibroblasts in an MMC
18 environment using an array of various crowding agents. Each tested crowder type had a
19 notably different effect on gene expression after two and four days of culture. However, the
20 phenotypic drift that they observed was in the form of downregulation of all genes of interest
21 (*COL1A1*, *COL1A3*, *FNI*, *PLOD2*, *ACTA2*, *MMP1*), and occurred basically in all tested
22 MMC environments (including Ficoll mix). They therefore concluded that an external pro-
23 fibrotic stimulus is needed for this cell type, such as TGF-beta 1, to continue with anti-fibrotic
24 drug screening. Simulation of a fibrotic response in normal human lung fibroblasts cultivated
25 in Ficoll mix with TGF-beta 1 by Rønnow *et al.*³⁷ increased the synthesis of collagen type I,
26 III and VI, fibronectin and alpha-smooth muscle actin. Similarly, Juhl *et al.*³⁶ described
27 different effects on gene expression and ECM production induced by pro-fibrotic stimulation
28 of normal human dermal fibroblasts cultivated in MMC (Ficoll mix) with TGF-beta 1, PDGF
29 or IL-6. TGF-beta 1 elicited a typical pro-fibrotic response in healthy cells by stimulating
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 gene expression of various ECM proteins (fibronectin, collagen type I, III, VI, and also type
4
5 IV and V), alpha-smooth muscle actin and TGF-beta 1 itself. They chose this approach due to
6
7 limited access to pathological cells from patients with systemic sclerosis or pulmonary
8
9 fibrosis, which are known to behave differently.³⁶ In contrast, clubfoot-derived pathological
10
11 cells (CF-M) expressed a similar expression profile already after short exposition to an MMC
12
13 environment even without TGF-beta 1 supplementation. Given the general similarities in
14
15 fibrotic processes, it is likely that MMC models consisting of normal fibroblasts with an
16
17 adequately selected crowding agent and pro-fibrotic stimuli that elicit the same response or a
18
19 similar response as clubfoot-derived cells, could produce results that are translatable to
20
21 relapsed clubfoot and *vice versa*.
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

29 In the next part of our study, we employed the established MMC environment of Fc18 as a
30
31 biomimetic model of clubfoot fibrosis to evaluate the effect of minoxidil (MXD). Minoxidil
32
33 has been approved by the U. S. Federal Drug Administration (FDA) for hypertension and hair
34
35 loss treatment (for a review, see Gupta *et al.*⁶⁸). Due to the function of MXD as a nonspecific
36
37 inhibitor of lysyl hydroxylase enzymes that catalyses the formation of pyridinoline cross-links
38
39 in collagen, it was also explored as a promising anti-fibrotic agent. Researchers tested its
40
41 properties in cultures of human fibroblasts from normal dermis or keloid and in
42
43 keratinocytes,^{49,69,70} in primary fibroblastic synovial cells,⁷¹ and after administration to mice to
44
45 alleviate pulmonary fibrosis,⁶⁰ with very satisfactory results. Previous results of our group had
46
47 shown the effect of MXD for the first time in clubfoot-derived fibroblasts.²² Here, we
48
49 correlate and expand on these results with more in-depth analyses to explore and compare the
50
51 effect of MXD in a standard cell culture and in an MMC environment.
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 Following the dose-dependent inhibitory effect of MXD on cell proliferation across a range
4 of concentrations (0 - 2 mM) in both Ctrl and Fc18 media, we observed a moderately positive
5
6 of concentrations (0 - 2 mM) in both Ctrl and Fc18 media, we observed a moderately positive
7
8 effect of Fc18 on cell proliferation during a 164-hour experiment. In both cases, we
9
10 determined 0.75 mM of MXD as the highest safe concentration for CF-M cells. At this
11
12 concentration of MXD, the cell count measured at the end of the experiment had dropped to
13
14 approx. 40-50% in comparison to the cells growing in both media without MXD. The
15
16 proliferation of CF-M cultivated with 0.5 and 0.75 mM slows down significantly after day 4
17
18 of culture, but this did not cause direct cytotoxicity.²² The same effect was reported for dermal
19
20 fibroblasts.⁶⁹ Limiting the proliferation of cells in a fibrotic environment could be an added
21
22 benefit to the anti-fibrotic action of the tested drug. We therefore reduced the tested
23
24 concentrations for further analyses accordingly.
25
26
27
28
29
30

31 The higher initial seeding density of cells in the experiments regarding collagen production
32
33 erased practically any inhibitory effect of 0.25 mM MXD on cell proliferation in both Ctrl and
34
35 Fc18 media. The inhibition was attenuated in the case of 0.5 mM MXD, but stayed the same
36
37 as before when 0.75 mM MXD was added. Since the cell proliferation was similar in the
38
39 MXD group in both media environments, we evaluated the collagen type I deposition per cell
40
41 this time. The collagen deposition in the Ctrl media declined with gradually increasing MXD
42
43 concentrations, following the same trend in the percentage decrease in collagen deposition as
44
45 in our previous study.²² In the Fc18 media, however, the gradual decrease in collagen was less
46
47 pronounced. When we compared the mean percentages of each group, the slope was very
48
49 similar to our previous results with the same MXD concentrations in the Ctrl media after three
50
51 weeks of cultivation in the same study. Such similarities indicate that it is effective to
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 accelerate collagen deposition via the Fc18 environment. Concentrations of 0.5 and 0.75 mM
4
5 of MXD significantly reduced the collagen deposition in both culture environments.
6
7

8 Similarly as in the study of Zuurmond *et al.*,⁴⁹ the gene expression analysis after 24 hours of
9
10 MXD supplementation to the cells revealed a significant decrease in all three isoforms of
11
12 lysyl hydroxylases (LH1, LH2, LH3) in the Ctrl and Fc18 media. Moreover, MXD entirely
13
14 prevented the increase in LH expression that we had observed in cells under the influence of
15
16 the base Fc18 media. The expression of LHs in MXD-treated Fc18 was inhibited to the same
17
18 extent as (in the case of LH1, LH3) or significantly more than (in the case of LH2) the
19
20 expression in MXD-treated Ctrl. At the same time, we detected no significant changes in gene
21
22 expression for procollagen chains (*COL1A1*, *COL1A2*). A study by Shao *et al.*⁶⁰ detected an
23
24 increase in the expression of genes for LH1, LH2 and LH3 in the serum of patients with
25
26 idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis, and also as in the lung tissue of the mice fibrosis model
27
28 induced by bleomycin in comparison with healthy animals. After they treated these mice with
29
30 MXD, the *in vivo* expression levels were still significantly higher than in the control. In the
31
32 studies of Zuurmond *et al.*⁴⁹ and Sarkovich *et al.*⁷¹, and also in a previous study of our
33
34 group,²² the addition of MXD alone did not affect the expression of procollagen chains at any
35
36 time interval. Unfortunately, Shao *et al.*⁶⁰ did not measure changes in any reported genes
37
38 outside the bleomycin group. The main inhibitory effect of MXD on collagen deposition is
39
40 thus realised through the downregulation of collagen-modifying enzymes, e.g. lysyl
41
42 hydroxylases, and by limiting the amount of hydroxylysine for hydroxyallysine cross-link
43
44 formation in collagen.^{53,72}
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 The effectiveness of MXD in reducing the hydroxyproline content and the pyridinium cross-
4 links (pyridinoline, deoxypyridinoline) that are elevated in models of fibrotic diseases were
5 documented in studies with the use of MMC environments⁶⁰ and without the use of MMC
6 environments.⁷¹ The long-term impact on the extracellular matrix deposited by CF-M cells
7 cultured under MXD influence for 16 days was amplified in our model environment,
8 represented by crowded Fc18 media. The combined effect of MXD and Fc18 produced
9 significantly greater inhibition of collagen deposition and greater inhibition of collagen cross-
10 linking. Although the potential of MXD as an anti-fibrotic agent has been recognised, its
11 influence on reducing each individual isoform of lysyl hydroxylase differs.^{49,60} Considering
12 the predominant role of hydroxyallysine cross-links mediated by lysyl hydroxylase 2 in
13 fibrosis, the search for a structural analog or derivative that would serve as its targeted
14 inhibitor^{73,74} is an important topic for future studies.

34 **Conclusions**

35
36 Our study has presented a unique analysis of an *in vitro* fibrosis model combining cells
37 derived from the contracted tissues of relapsed clubfoot patients with a biomimetic cultivation
38 environment induced by macromolecular crowding (MMC). Mixed MMC of differentially
39 sized Ficolls applied at 18% FVO provided the most favourable conditions of all tested
40 variants, outperforming Polyvinylpyrrolidone. The environment induced by Ficoll stimulated
41 the expression of fibrosis-related markers in clubfoot-derived cells, which is consistent with
42 the results of the original contracted tissue analysis. It also promoted the *in vitro* conversion
43 rate of soluble collagen into insoluble collagen, while markedly enhancing collagen
44 deposition and supramolecular assembly during short-term experiments. A prolonged
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 cultivation mode enabled the formation of a thick layer of mature extracellular matrix, which
4
5 we used to evaluate minoxidil as a potential anti-fibrotic agent. The application of minoxidil
6
7 confirmed a dose-dependent effect on the reduction of collagen deposition, and revealed a
8
9 marked reduction of collagen cross-linking in the extracellular matrix of clubfoot-derived
10
11 cells. Our model environment enhanced both effects.
12
13
14

15
16 Our findings set a basis for broadening research on clubfoot by a) defining the parameters
17
18 of clubfoot fibrosis and b) setting a simple pseudo-3D *in vitro* model of clubfoot fibrosis. The
19
20 parameters of this model are transferable and can be simulated even without access to
21
22 clubfoot-derived cells, e.g. with healthy fibroblasts and appropriate pro-fibrotic stimuli in a
23
24 crowded cell culture environment for the purpose of drug testing.
25
26
27

28
29 A macromolecularly crowded cell culture brings the benefit of a biomimetic environment
30
31 and an option of short cultivation periods, creating a high-throughput platform for drug
32
33 screening and for early drug development studies. The application of our findings in a
34
35 standard cell culture or in combination with 3D biofabricated scaffolds or decellularised tissue
36
37 slices in the future can facilitate the search for potential treatments to reverse local fibrosis,
38
39 including less research-exposed conditions such as clubfoot.
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47

48 **Supporting Information:** Additional experimental data, table and figures describing tissue
49
50 sample donors, methodology and results of proliferation and cytotoxicity assays (PDF).
51
52

53 **Author contributions:** Conceptualisation - M.D.; methodology - M.D., J.K. and T.N.;
54
55 investigation - M.D., J.K., D.V., A.E. and T.N.; data analysis - M.D., J.K. and T.N.; resources
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 - M.O.; data curation - M.D., T.N., M.O.; writing - original draft preparation - M.D.; writing -
4
5 review and editing - J.K., D.V., A.E., T.N., M.O., E.F., and L.B.; visualisation - M.D.;
6
7 supervision - E.F. and L.B.; project administration - M.D.; funding acquisition - M.D., A.E.
8
9 and L.B. The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have
10
11 given approval to the final version of the manuscript.
12
13
14

15
16
17 **Funding:** This work was supported by Charles University [project GA UK No. 410121], the
18
19 Ministry of Health of the Czech Republic [AZV NU22-10-00072], the *Praemium Academiae*
20
21 grant [No. AP2202] provided by the Czech Academy of Sciences, and project No.
22
23 CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004562 of the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports (MEYS),
24
25 which was co-funded by the European Union. We would also like to acknowledge support
26
27 from the Bioimaging core facility of the Institute of Physiology ASCR (IPHYS BIF), which is
28
29 funded by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports (MEYS) [Large RI Project
30
31 LM2023050 Czech-BioImaging] and the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)
32
33 [project No. CZ.02.1.01/0.0/0.0/18_046/0016045].
34
35
36
37

38
39 **Acknowledgements:** We would like to gratefully acknowledge the staff of Bulovka Hospital
40
41 for their cooperation in sample acquisition and storage, Marta Vandrovцова, Ph.D. (Inst.
42
43 Physiol., Czech Acad. Sci.) for proofreading, and Mr. Robin Healey (Czech Technical Univ.,
44
45 Prague) for his language revision of the manuscript.
46
47
48

49
50 **Data Availability Statement:** The data supporting the conclusions of this study are available
51
52 within this article and its Supporting Information file or from the corresponding author upon
53
54 reasonable request.
55
56

57 58 59 60 **References**

- 1
2
3 (1) Ansar, A.; Rahman, A. E.; Romero, L.; Haider, M. R.; Rahman, M. M.; Moinuddin, M.;
4 Siddique, M. A. B.; Mamun, M. A.; Mazumder, T.; Pirani, S. P.; Mathias, R. G.; Arifeen,
5 S. E.; Hoque, D. M. E. Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Global Birth Prevalence
6 of Clubfoot: A Study Protocol. *BMJ Open* **2018**, *8* (3), e019246. DOI: 10.1136/bmjopen-
7 2017-019246.
8
9
- 10 (2) Ippolito, E. Update on Pathologic Anatomy of Clubfoot. *J. Pediatr. Orthop. B* **1995**, *4* (1),
11 17–24. DOI: 10.1097/01202412-199504010-00003.
- 12 (3) Foster, A.; Davis, N. Congenital Talipes Equinovarus (Clubfoot). *Surgery* **2007**, *25* (4),
13 171–175. DOI: 10.1016/j.mpsur.2007.04.001.
- 14 (4) Dobbs, M. B.; Gurnett, C. A. Update on Clubfoot: Etiology and Treatment. *Clin. Orthop.*
15 *Relat. Res.* **2009**, *467* (5), 1146–1153. DOI: 10.1007/s11999-009-0734-9.
- 16 (5) Agarwal, A.; Rastogi, A.; Rastogi, P. Relapses in Clubfoot Treated with Ponseti
17 Technique and Standard Bracing Protocol - a Systematic Analysis. *J Clin. Orthop.*
18 *Trauma.* **2021**, *18*, 199–204. DOI: 10.1016/j.jcot.2021.04.029.
- 19 (6) Schelven, H. van; Moerman, S.; Steen, M. van der; Besselaar, A. T.; Greve, C. Prognostic
20 Factors for Recurrent Idiopathic Clubfoot Deformity: A Systematic Literature Review and
21 Meta-Analysis. *Acta Orthop.* **2022**, 11–28. DOI: 10.1080/17453674.2021.1982576.
- 22 (7) Ošťádal, M.; Chomiak, J.; Dungl, P.; Frydrychová, M.; Burian, M. Comparison of the
23 Short-Term and Long-Term Results of the Ponseti Method in the Treatment of Idiopathic
24 Pes Equinovarus. *Internat. Orthop.* **2013**, *37* (9), 1821–1825. DOI: 10.1007/s00264-013-
25 2033-z.
26
27
- 28 (8) Cummings, R. J. The Effectiveness of Botulinum A Toxin as an Adjunct to the Treatment
29 of Clubfeet by the Ponseti Method: A Randomized, Double Blind, Placebo Controlled
30 Study. *J. Pediatr. Orthop.* **2009**, *29* (6), 564–569. DOI: 10.1097/BPO.0b013e3181b2f21d.
- 31 (9) Alvarez, C. M.; Wright, J. G.; Chhina, H.; Howren, A.; Law, P. Botulinum Toxin Type A
32 Versus Placebo for Idiopathic Clubfoot: A Two-Center, Double-Blind, Randomized
33 Controlled Trial. *J. Bone Joint Surg. Am.* **2018**, *100* (18), 1589–1596. DOI:
34 10.2106/JBJS.17.01652.
35
36
- 37 (10) Fietzek, U. M.; Kossmehl, P.; Schelosky, L.; Ebersbach, G.; Wissel, J. Early
38 Botulinum Toxin Treatment for Spastic Pes Equinovarus - a Randomized Double-Blind
39 Placebo-Controlled Study. *Eur. J. Neurol.* **2014**, *21* (8), 1089–1095. DOI:
40 10.1111/ene.12381.
41
42
- 43 (11) Fukuhara, K.; Schollmeier, G.; Uthhoff, H. K. The Pathogenesis of Club Foot. A
44 Histomorphometric and Immunohistochemical Study of Fetuses. *J. Bone Joint Surg. Br.*
45 **1994**, *76* (3), 450–457. DOI: 10.1302/0301-620X.76B3.8175852.
- 46 (12) Zimny, M. L.; Willig, S. J.; Roberts, J. M.; D'Ambrosia, R. D. An Electron
47 Microscopic Study of the Fascia from the Medial and Lateral Sides of Clubfoot. *J.*
48 *Pediatr. Orthop.* **1985**, *5* (5), 577–581. DOI: 10.1097/01241398-198509000-00014.
- 49 (13) Sano, H.; Uthhoff, H. K.; Jarvis, J. G.; Mansingh, A.; Wenckebach, G. F. Pathogenesis
50 of Soft-Tissue Contracture in Club Foot. *J. Bone Joint Surg. Br.* **1998**, *80* (4), 641–644.
51 DOI: 10.1302/0301-620X.80B4.0800641.
52
53
- 54 (14) Li, C.; Nguyen, Q.; Cole, W. G.; Alman, B. A. Potential Treatment for Clubfeet Based
55 on Growth Factor Blockade. *J. Pediatr. Orthop.* **2001**, *21* (3), 372–377. DOI:
56 10.1097/01241398-200105000-00021.
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3
4 (15) Poon, R.; Li, C.; Alman, B. A. Beta-Catenin Mediates Soft Tissue Contracture in
5 Clubfoot. *Clin. Orthop. Relat. R.* **2009**, *467* (5), 1180–1185. DOI: 10.1007/s11999-008-
6 0692-7.
- 7 (16) Ošťádal, M.; Eckhardt, A.; Herget, J.; Mikšík, I.; Dungl, P.; Chomiak, J.; Frydrychová,
8 M.; Burian, M. Proteomic Analysis of the Extracellular Matrix in Idiopathic Pes
9 Equinovarus. *Mol. Cell. Biochem.* **2015**, *401* (1–2), 133–139. DOI: 10.1007/s11010-014-
10 2300-3.
- 11 (17) Eckhardt, A.; Novotny, T.; Doubkova, M.; Hronkova, L.; Vajner, L.; Pataridis, S.;
12 Hadraba, D.; Kulhava, L.; Plencner, M.; Knitlova, J.; Liskova, J.; Uhlík, J.; Zaloudikova,
13 M.; Vondrasek, D.; Miksik, I.; Ostadal, M. Novel Contribution to Clubfoot Pathogenesis:
14 The Possible Role of Extracellular Matrix Proteins. *J. Orthop. Res.* **2019**, *37* (3), 769–778.
15 DOI: 10.1002/jor.24211.
- 16 (18) Knitlova, J.; Doubkova, M.; Eckhardt, A.; Ostadal, M.; Musilkova, J.; Bacakova, L.;
17 Novotny, T. Increased Collagen Crosslinking in Stiff Clubfoot Tissue: Implications for
18 the Improvement of Therapeutic Strategies. *IJMS* **2021**, *22* (21), 11903. DOI:
19 10.3390/ijms22111903.
- 20 (19) Novotny, T.; Eckhardt, A.; Doubkova, M.; Knitlova, J.; Vondrasek, D.; Vanaskova,
21 E.; Ostadal, M.; Uhlík, J.; Bacakova, L.; Musilkova, J. The Possible Role of Hypoxia in
22 the Affected Tissue of Relapsed Clubfoot. *Sci. Rep.* **2022**, *12* (1), 1–10. DOI:
23 10.1038/s41598-022-08519-z.
- 24 (20) Vondrášek, D.; Hadraba, D.; Příbyl, J.; Eckhardt, A.; Ošťádal, M.; Lopot, F.; Jelen, K.;
25 Doubková, M.; Knitlová, J.; Novotný, T.; Janáček, J. Microstructural Analysis of
26 Collagenous Structures in Relapsed Clubfoot Tissue. *Microsc. Microanal.* **2023**, *29* (1),
27 265–272. DOI: 10.1093/micmic/ozac012.
- 28 (21) Siani, A. Pharmacological Treatment of Fibrosis: A Systematic Review of Clinical
29 Trials. *SN Compr. Clin. Med.* **2020**, *2* (5), 531–550. DOI: 10.1007/s42399-020-00292-2.
- 30 (22) Knitlova, J.; Doubkova, M.; Plencner, M.; Vondrasek, D.; Eckhardt, A.; Ostadal, M.;
31 Musilkova, J.; Bacakova, L.; Novotny, T. Minoxidil Decreases Collagen I Deposition and
32 Tissue-like Contraction in Clubfoot-Derived Cells: A Way to Improve Conservative
33 Treatment of Relapsed Clubfoot? *Connect. Tissue Res.* **2021**, *62* (5), 554–569. DOI:
34 10.1080/03008207.2020.1816992.
- 35 (23) Lareu, R. R.; Subramhanya, K. H.; Peng, Y.; Benny, P.; Chen, C.; Wang, Z.;
36 Rajagopalan, R.; Raghunath, M. Collagen Matrix Deposition Is Dramatically Enhanced in
37 Vitro When Crowded with Charged Macromolecules: The Biological Relevance of the
38 Excluded Volume Effect. *FEBS Letters* **2007**, *581* (14), 2709–2714. DOI:
39 10.1016/j.febslet.2007.05.020.
- 40 (24) Benny, P.; Raghunath, M. Making Microenvironments: A Look into Incorporating
41 Macromolecular Crowding into in Vitro Experiments, to Generate Biomimetic
42 Microenvironments Which Are Capable of Directing Cell Function for Tissue
43 Engineering Applications. *J. Tissue Eng.* **2017**, *8*. DOI: 10.1177/2041731417730467.
- 44 (25) Tsiapalis, D.; Zeugolis, D. I. It Is Time to Crowd Your Cell Culture Media –
45 Physicochemical Considerations with Biological Consequences. *Biomaterials* **2021**, *275*,
46 120943. DOI: 10.1016/j.biomaterials.2021.120943.
- 47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3
4 (26) Bateman, J. F.; Cole, W. G.; Pillow, J. J.; Ramshaw, J. A. Induction of Procollagen
5 Processing in Fibroblast Cultures by Neutral Polymers. *J. Biol. Chem.* **1986**, *261* (9),
6 4198–4203. DOI: 10.1016/S0021-9258(17)35645-4.
- 7 (27) Hojima, Y.; Behta, B.; Romanic, A. M.; Prockop, D. J. Cleavage of Type I
8 Procollagen by C- and N-Proteinases Is More Rapid If the Substrate Is Aggregated with
9 Dextran Sulfate or Polyethylene Glycol. *Anal. Biochem.* **1994**, *223* (2), 173–180. DOI:
10 10.1006/abio.1994.1569.
- 11 (28) Lareu, R.; Arsianti, I.; Subramhanya, H.; Yanxian, P.; Raghunath, M. In Vitro
12 Enhancement of Collagen Matrix Formation and Crosslinking for Applications in Tissue
13 Engineering: A Preliminary Study. *Tissue engineering* **2007**, *13*, 385–391. DOI:
14 10.1089/ten.2006.0224.
- 15 (29) Chen, C.; Peng, Y.; Wang, Z.; Fish, P.; Kaar, J.; Koepsel, R.; Russell, A.; Lareu, R.;
16 Raghunath, M. The Scar-in-a-Jar: Studying Potential Antifibrotic Compounds from the
17 Epigenetic to Extracellular Level in a Single Well. *Br. J. Pharmacol.* **2009**, *158* (5), 1196–
18 1209. DOI: 10.1111/j.1476-5381.2009.00387.x.
- 19 (30) Zeiger, A. S.; Loe, F. C.; Li, R.; Raghunath, M.; Vliet, K. J. V. Macromolecular
20 Crowding Directs Extracellular Matrix Organization and Mesenchymal Stem Cell
21 Behavior. *PLOS ONE* **2012**, *7*(5), e37904. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0037904.
- 22 (31) Kumar, P.; Satyam, A.; Fan, X.; Collin, E.; Rochev, Y.; Rodriguez, B. J.; Gorelov, A.;
23 Dillon, S.; Joshi, L.; Raghunath, M.; Pandit, A.; Zeugolis, D. I. Macromolecularly
24 Crowded in Vitro Microenvironments Accelerate the Production of Extracellular Matrix-
25 Rich Supramolecular Assemblies. *Sci. Rep.* **2015**, *5*(1), 8729. DOI: 10.1038/srep08729.
- 26 (32) Good, R. B.; Eley, J. D.; Gower, E.; Butt, G.; Blanchard, A. D.; Fisher, A. J.;
27 Nanthakumar, C. B. A High Content, Phenotypic ‘Scar-in-a-Jar’ Assay for Rapid
28 Quantification of Collagen Fibrillogenesis Using Disease-Derived Pulmonary Fibroblasts.
29 *BMC Biomed. Eng.* **2019**, *1* (1), 14. DOI: 10.1186/s42490-019-0014-z.
- 30 (33) Puerta Cavanzo, N.; Bigaeva, E.; Boersema, M.; Olinga, P.; Bank, R. Macromolecular
31 Crowding as a Tool to Screen Anti-Fibrotic Drugs: The Scar-in-a-Jar System Revisited.
32 *Front. Med.* **2021**, *7*. DOI: 10.3389/fmed.2020.615774.
- 33 (34) Coentro, J. Q.; di Nubila, A.; May, U.; Prince, S.; Zwaagstra, J.; Järvinen, T. A. H.;
34 Zeugolis, D. I. Dual Drug Delivery Collagen Vehicles for Modulation of Skin Fibrosis in
35 Vitro. *Biomed. Mater.* **2022**, *17*(2), 025017. DOI: 10.1088/1748-605X/ac5673.
- 36 (35) Rosell-Garcia, T.; Rodriguez-Pascual, F. Enhancement of Collagen Deposition and
37 Cross-Linking by Coupling Lysyl Oxidase with Bone Morphogenetic Protein-1 and Its
38 Application in Tissue Engineering. *Sci. Rep.* **2018**, *8*. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-018-29236-6.
- 39 (36) Juhl, P.; Bondesen, S.; Hawkins, C. L.; Karsdal, M. A.; Bay-Jensen, A.-C.; Davies, M.
40 J.; Siebuhr, A. S. Dermal Fibroblasts Have Different Extracellular Matrix Profiles
41 Induced by TGF- β , PDGF and IL-6 in a Model for Skin Fibrosis. *Sci. Rep.* **2020**, *10* (1),
42 17300. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-020-74179-6.
- 43 (37) Rønnow, S. R.; Dabbagh, R. Q.; Genovese, F.; Nanthakumar, C. B.; Barrett, V. J.;
44 Good, R. B.; Brockbank, S.; Cruwys, S.; Jessen, H.; Sorensen, G. L.; Karsdal, M. A.;
45 Leeming, D. J.; Sand, J. M. B. Prolonged Scar-in-a-Jar: An in Vitro Screening Tool for
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 Anti-Fibrotic Therapies Using Biomarkers of Extracellular Matrix Synthesis. *Respir. Res.*
4 **2020**, *21* (1), 108. DOI: 10.1186/s12931-020-01369-1.
- 5
6 (38) Rashid, R.; Lim, N.; Chee, S.; Png, S.; Wohland, T.; Raghunath, M. Novel Use for
7 Polyvinylpyrrolidone as a Macromolecular Crowder for Enhanced Extracellular Matrix
8 Deposition and Cell Proliferation. *Tissue Eng. Part C-Meth.* **2014**, *20*. DOI:
9 10.1089/ten.TEC.2013.0733.
- 10
11 (39) Cigognini, D.; Gaspar, D.; Kumar, P.; Satyam, A.; Alagesan, S.; Sanz-Nogués, C.;
12 Griffin, M.; O'Brien, T.; Pandit, A.; Zeugolis, D. I. Macromolecular Crowding Meets
13 Oxygen Tension in Human Mesenchymal Stem Cell Culture - A Step Closer to
14 Physiologically Relevant in Vitro Organogenesis. *Sci. Rep.* **2016**, *6* (1), 30746. DOI:
15 10.1038/srep30746.
- 16
17 (40) Graceffa, V.; Zeugolis, D. Carrageenan Enhances Chondrogenesis and Osteogenesis in
18 Human Bone Marrow Stem Cell Culture. *eCM* **2019**, *37*, 310–332. DOI:
19 10.22203/eCM.v037a19.
- 20
21 (41) De Pieri, A.; Korntner, S. H.; Capella-Monsonis, H.; Tsiapalis, D.; Kostjuk, S. V.;
22 Churbanov, S.; Timashev, P.; Gorelov, A.; Rochev, Y.; Zeugolis, D. I. Macromolecular
23 Crowding Transforms Regenerative Medicine by Enabling the Accelerated Development
24 of Functional and Truly Three-Dimensional Cell Assembled Micro Tissues. *Biomaterials*
25 **2022**, *287*, 121674. DOI: 10.1016/j.biomaterials.2022.121674.
- 26
27 (42) Graham, J.; Raghunath, M.; Vogel, V. Fibrillar Fibronectin Plays a Key Role as
28 Nucleator of Collagen I Polymerization during Macromolecular Crowding-Enhanced
29 Matrix Assembly. *Biomater. Sci.* **2019**, *7*(11), 4519–4535. DOI: 10.1039/c9bm00868c.
- 30
31 (43) Wong, C.-W.; LeGrand, C. F.; Kinnear, B. F.; Sobota, R. M.; Ramalingam, R.; Dye,
32 D. E.; Raghunath, M.; Lane, E. B.; Coombe, D. R. In Vitro Expansion of Keratinocytes
33 on Human Dermal Fibroblast-Derived Matrix Retains Their Stem-Like Characteristics.
34 *Sci. Rep.* **2019**, *9*(1), 18561. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-019-54793-9.
- 35
36 (44) Coentro, J. Q.; May, U.; Prince, S.; Zwaagstra, J.; Ritvos, O.; Järvinen, T. A. H.;
37 Zeugolis, D. I. Adapting the Scar-in-a-Jar to Skin Fibrosis and Screening Traditional and
38 Contemporary Anti-Fibrotic Therapies. *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* **2021**, *9*, 756399. DOI:
39 10.3389/fbioe.2021.756399.
- 40
41 (45) Satyam, A.; Kumar, P.; Fan, X.; Gorelov, A.; Rochev, Y.; Joshi, L.; Peinado, H.;
42 Lyden, D.; Thomas, B.; Rodriguez, B.; Raghunath, M.; Pandit, A.; Zeugolis, D.
43 Macromolecular Crowding Meets Tissue Engineering by Self-Assembly: A Paradigm
44 Shift in Regenerative Medicine. *Adv. Mater.* **2014**, *26* (19), 3024–3034. DOI:
45 10.1002/adma.201304428.
- 46
47 (46) Tsiapalis, D.; Kearns, S.; Kelly, J. L.; Zeugolis, D. I. Growth Factor and
48 Macromolecular Crowding Supplementation in Human Tenocyte Culture. *Biomaterials*
49 *and Biosystems* **2021**, *1*, 100009. DOI: 10.1016/j.bbiosy.2021.100009.
- 50
51 (47) Alvarado, D. M.; McCall, K.; Aferol, H.; Silva, M. J.; Garbow, J. R.; Spees, W. M.;
52 Patel, T.; Siegel, M.; Dobbs, M. B.; Gurnett, C. A. Pitx1 Haploinsufficiency Causes
53 Clubfoot in Humans and a Clubfoot-like Phenotype in Mice. *Hum. Mol. Genet.* **2011**, *20*
54 (20), 3943–3952. DOI: 10.1093/hmg/ddr313.
- 55
56 (48) Collinson, J. M.; Lindström, N. O.; Neves, C.; Wallace, K.; Meharg, C.; Charles, R.
57 H.; Ross, Z. K.; Fraser, A. M.; Mbogo, I.; Oras, K.; Nakamoto, M.; Barker, S.; Duce, S.;
58
59
60

- Miedzybrodzka, Z.; Vargesson, N. The Developmental and Genetic Basis of ‘Clubfoot’ in the Peroneal Muscular Atrophy Mutant Mouse. *Development* **2018**, *145* (3), dev160093. DOI: 10.1242/dev.160093.
- (49) Zuurmond, A.; Vanderslotverhoeven, A.; Vandura, E.; Degroot, J.; Bank, R. Minoxidil Exerts Different Inhibitory Effects on Gene Expression of Lysyl Hydroxylase 1, 2, and 3: Implications for Collagen Cross-Linking and Treatment of Fibrosis. *Matrix Biol.* **2005**, *24* (4), 261–270. DOI: 10.1016/j.matbio.2005.04.002.
- (50) Bailey, A. J.; Bazin, S.; Sims, T. J.; Le Lous, M.; Nicoletis, C.; Delaunay, A. Characterization of the Collagen of Human Hypertrophic and Normal Scars. *BBA - Protein Struct.* **1975**, *405* (2), 412–421. DOI: 10.1016/0005-2795(75)90106-3.
- (51) van der Slot, A. J.; Zuurmond, A.-M.; van den Bogaerdt, A. J.; Ulrich, M. M. W.; Middelkoop, E.; Boers, W.; Karel Runday, H.; DeGroot, J.; Huizinga, T. W. J.; Bank, R. A. Increased Formation of Pyridinoline Cross-Links Due to Higher Telopeptide Lysyl Hydroxylase Levels Is a General Fibrotic Phenomenon. *Matrix Biol.* **2004**, *23* (4), 251–257. DOI: 10.1016/j.matbio.2004.06.001.
- (52) van der Slot-Verhoeven, A. J.; van Dura, E. A.; Attema, J.; Blauw, B.; DeGroot, J.; Huizinga, T. W. J.; Zuurmond, A.-M.; Bank, R. A. The Type of Collagen Cross-Link Determines the Reversibility of Experimental Skin Fibrosis. *BBA - Mol. Basis Dis.* **2005**, *1740* (1), 60–67. DOI: 10.1016/j.bbadis.2005.02.007.
- (53) Piersma, B.; Bank, R. A. Collagen Cross-Linking Mediated by Lysyl Hydroxylase 2: An Enzymatic Battlefield to Combat Fibrosis. *Essays Biochem.* **2019**, *63* (3), 377–387. DOI: 10.1042/EBC20180051.
- (54) Schindelin, J.; Arganda-Carreras, I.; Frise, E.; Kaynig, V.; Longair, M.; Pietzsch, T.; Preibisch, S.; Rueden, C.; Saalfeld, S.; Schmid, B.; Tinevez, J.-Y.; White, D. J.; Hartenstein, V.; Eliceiri, K.; Tomancak, P.; Cardona, A. Fiji: An Open-Source Platform for Biological-Image Analysis. *Nat. Methods* **2012**, *9* (7), 676–682. DOI: 10.1038/nmeth.2019.
- (55) Schmidt, U.; Weigert, M.; Broaddus, C.; Myers, G. Cell Detection with Star-Convex Polygons. In *Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention – MICCAI 2018*; Frangi, A. F., Schnabel, J. A., Davatzikos, C., Alberola-López, C., Fichtinger, G., Eds.; Springer International Publishing: Cham, 2018; pp 265–273. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-00934-2_30.
- (56) Lareu, R. R.; Zeugolis, D. I.; Abu-Rub, M.; Pandit, A.; Raghunath, M. Essential Modification of the Sircol Collagen Assay for the Accurate Quantification of Collagen Content in Complex Protein Solutions. *Acta Biomater.* **2010**, *6* (8), 3146–3151. DOI: 10.1016/j.actbio.2010.02.004.
- (57) *Methods in Molecular Medicine, Vol. 101: Cartilage and Osteoarthritis, Volume 2: Structure and In Vivo Analysis*; De Ceuninck, F., Sabatini, M., Pastoureau, P., Eds.; Methods in Molecular Medicine; Humana Press, 2004. ISBN: 978-1-58829-505-7.
- (58) Chen, C.; Loe, F.; Blocki, A.; Peng, Y.; Raghunath, M. Applying Macromolecular Crowding to Enhance Extracellular Matrix Deposition and Its Remodeling in Vitro for Tissue Engineering and Cell-Based Therapies. *Adv. Drug Deliver. Rev.* **2011**, *63* (4–5), 277–290. DOI: 10.1016/j.addr.2011.03.003.

- 1
2
3
4 (59) Green, N. H.; Delaine-Smith, R. M.; Askew, H. J.; Byers, R.; Reilly, G. C.; Matcher,
5 S. J. A New Mode of Contrast in Biological Second Harmonic Generation Microscopy.
6 *Sci. Rep.* **2017**, *7*, 13331. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-017-13752-y.
- 7
8 (60) Shao, S.; Zhang, X.; Duan, L.; Fang, H.; Rao, S.; Liu, W.; Guo, B.; Zhang, X. Lysyl
9 Hydroxylase Inhibition by Minoxidil Blocks Collagen Deposition and Prevents
10 Pulmonary Fibrosis via TGF-B1/Smad3 Signaling Pathway. *Med. Sci. Monit.* **2018**, *24*,
11 8592–8601. DOI: 10.12659/MSM.910761.
- 12
13 (61) Capella-Monsonís, H.; Coentro, J. Q.; Graceffa, V.; Wu, Z.; Zeugolis, D. I. An
14 Experimental Toolbox for Characterization of Mammalian Collagen Type I in Biological
15 Specimens. *Nat. Protoc.* **2018**, *13* (3), 507–529. DOI: 10.1038/nprot.2017.117.
- 16
17 (62) Kumar, P.; Satyam, A.; Gaspar, D.; Cigognini, D.; Sanz-Nogués, C.; O'Brien, T.;
18 Pandit, A.; Zeugolis, D. Macromolecular Crowding: The Next Frontier in Tissue
19 Engineering. *Adv. Sci. Tech.* **2014**, *96*, 1–8. DOI: 10.4028/www.scientific.net/AST.96.1.
- 20
21 (63) Louisthelmy, R.; Burke, B. M.; Cornelison, R. C. Brain Cancer Cell-Derived Matrices
22 and Effects on Astrocyte Migration. *Cells Tissues Organs* **2023**, *212* (1), 21–31. DOI:
23 10.1159/000522609.
- 24
25 (64) Ellis, R. J. Macromolecular Crowding: Obvious but Underappreciated. *Trends*
26 *Biochem. Sci.* **2001**, *26* (10), 597–604. DOI: 10.1016/S0968-0004(01)01938-7.
- 27
28 (65) Armstrong, J. K.; Wenby, R. B.; Meiselman, H. J.; Fisher, T. C. The Hydrodynamic
29 Radii of Macromolecules and Their Effect on Red Blood Cell Aggregation. *Biophys. J.*
30 **2004**, *87* (6), 4259–4270. DOI: 10.1529/biophysj.104.047746.
- 31
32 (66) Dewavrin, J.-Y.; Abdurrahim, M.; Blocki, A.; Musib, M.; Piazza, F.; Raghunath, M.
33 Synergistic Rate Boosting of Collagen Fibrillogenesis in Heterogeneous Mixtures of
34 Crowding Agents. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2015**, *119* (12), 4350–4358. DOI:
35 10.1021/jp5077559.
- 36
37 (67) Giannandrea, M.; Parks, W. C. Diverse Functions of Matrix Metalloproteinases during
38 Fibrosis. *Dis. Model. Mech.* **2014**, *7* (2), 193–203. DOI: 10.1242/dmm.012062.
- 39
40 (68) Gupta, A. K.; Talukder, M.; Venkataraman, M.; Bamimore, M. A. Minoxidil: A
41 Comprehensive Review. *J. Dermatol. Treat.* **2022**, *33* (4), 1896–1906. DOI:
42 10.1080/09546634.2021.1945527.
- 43
44 (69) Pinnell, S. R.; Murad, S. Effects of Minoxidil on Cultured Human Skin Fibroblasts.
45 *Dermatologica* **1987**, *175 Suppl 2*, 12–18. DOI: 10.1159/000248891.
- 46
47 (70) Priestley, G. C.; Lord, R.; Stavropoulos, P. The Metabolism of Fibroblasts from
48 Normal and Fibrotic Skin Is Inhibited by Minoxidil in Vitro. *Br. J. Dermatol.* **1991**, *125*
49 (3), 217–221. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2133.1991.tb14743.x.
- 50
51 (71) Sarkovich, S.; Issa, P. P.; Longanecker, A.; Martin, D.; Redondo, K.; McTernan, P.;
52 Simkin, J.; Marrero, L. Minoxidil Weakens Newly Synthesized Collagen in Fibrotic
53 Synoviocytes from Osteoarthritis Patients. *J. Exp. Orthop.* **2023**, *10* (1), 84. DOI:
54 10.1186/s40634-023-00650-8.
- 55
56 (72) Murad, S.; Pinnell, S. R. Suppression of Fibroblast Proliferation and Lysyl
57 Hydroxylase Activity by Minoxidil. *J. Biol. Chem.* **1987**, *262* (25), 11973–11978. DOI:
58 10.1016/S0021-9258(18)45304-5.
59
60

- 1
2
3 (73) Devkota, A. K.; Veloria, J. R.; Guo, H. F.; Kurie, J. M.; Cho, E. J.; Dalby, K. N.
4 Development of a High-Throughput Lysyl Hydroxylase (LH) Assay and Identification of
5 Small-Molecule Inhibitors against LH2. *SLAS discov.* **2019**, *24* (4), 484–491. DOI:
6 10.1177/2472555218817057.
7
8 (74) Maghsoud, Y.; Vázquez-Montelongo, E. A.; Yang, X.; Liu, C.; Jing, Z.; Lee, J.;
9 Harger, M.; Smith, A. K.; Espinoza, M.; Guo, H.-F.; Kurie, J. M.; Dalby, K. N.; Ren, P.;
10 Cisneros, G. A. Computational Investigation of a Series of Small Molecules as Potential
11 Compounds for Lysyl Hydroxylase-2 (LH2) Inhibition. *J. Chem. Inf. Model.* **2023**, *63* (3),
12 986–1001. DOI: 10.1021/acs.jcim.2c01448.
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

For Table of Contents Only

Created with BioRender.com

24 For Table of Contents Only

25 82x44mm (600 x 600 DPI)

Figure 1. Proliferation and extracellular type I collagen deposition of NHDF fibroblasts after 7 days of culture with/without MMC. (A) Cell proliferation in media with different MMC concentrations. Truncated violin plot, median with IQR (n=18-137). Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA, Dunn's test (vs. Ctrl). (B) Integrated fluorescence density of extracellular collagen relative to Ctrl (no MMC). Mean + SEM (n=5-6). Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA, Dunn's test (vs. Ctrl). (C) Demonstrative images of extracellular type I collagen deposition after fluorescent staining. Olympus IX51 microscope, 10× objective. Scale bar = 200 μ m.

178x125mm (243 x 243 DPI)

Figure 2. Proliferation and extracellular type I collagen deposition of non-contracted clubfoot-derived cells (CF-L) after 7 days of culture with/without MMC. (A) Cell proliferation in media with different MMC concentrations. Truncated violin plot, Median with IQR (n=10-54). Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA, Dunn's test (vs. Ctrl). (B) Integrated fluorescence density of extracellular collagen relative to Ctrl (without MMC). Mean + SEM (n=5-6). Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA, Dunn's test (vs. Ctrl). (C) Demonstrative images of extracellular type I collagen deposition after fluorescent staining. Olympus IX51 microscope, 10× objective. Scale bar = 200 μ m.

178x123mm (243 x 243 DPI)

29
30
31
32
33
34

Figure 3. Proliferation and extracellular type I collagen deposition of contracted clubfoot-derived cells (CF-M) after 7 days of culture with/without MMC. (A) Cell proliferation in media with different MMC concentrations. Truncated violin plot, median with IQR (n=24-75). Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA, Dunn's test (vs. Ctrl). (B) Integrated fluorescence density of extracellular collagen relative to Ctrl (without MMC). Mean + SEM (n=5-7). Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA, Dunn's test (vs. Ctrl). (C) Demonstrative images of extracellular type I collagen deposition after fluorescent staining. Olympus IX51 microscope, 10× objective. Scale bar = 200 μ m.

35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

178x125mm (243 x 243 DPI)

45 Figure 4. Maturation of collagen fibers. SHG imaging of type I collagen fibers after 7 days of cultivation of
46 normal human fibroblasts (NHDFs) and clubfoot-derived fibroblasts (CF-L, CF-M) with (Fc9, Fc18, PVP18) or
47 without (Ctrl) macromolecularly crowded media - demonstrative images. The red signal (upper row) is the
48 autofluorescence of cells. The green signal (lower row) is SHG. Leica DMI8 inverted microscope with a Leica
49 TCS SP8 X confocal unit, 63× water immersion objective. Scale bar = 50 μm .

50 84x122mm (243 x 243 DPI)

Figure 5. Analysis of collagen deposition by clubfoot-derived fibroblasts (CF-M) in distinct fractions of the sample during 16-day cultivation without (Ctrl) or with (Fc18) macromolecularly crowded media. (A) Collagen produced into cultivation media between media changes (n=6). (B) Soluble collagen newly deposited into the extracellular matrix of the cell layer (n=9). (C) Insoluble cross-linked collagen deposited into the extracellular matrix (n=11). (D) Total collagen deposited in the cell layer extracellular matrix (n=14). Scatter plots, Median with 95% CI. Paired t-test (****p<0.0001).

159x54mm (1200 x 1200 DPI)

Figure 6. Relative mRNA expression of genes in clubfoot-derived fibroblasts (CF-M) after 24 hours of cultivation without (Ctrl) or with (Fc18) a macromolecularly crowded environment. Genes of interest: COL1A1, COL1A2 (collagen type I alpha-1 and alpha-2 chains); COL3A1 (collagen type III alpha-1 chain); COL6A3 (collagen type VI alpha-3 chain); PLOD1, PLOD2, PLOD3 (lysyl hydroxylase 1, 2 and 3); LOX (lysyl oxidase); P4THM (prolyl-4-hydroxylase); FN1 (fibronectin 1); TGFB1 (transforming growth factor-beta 1); ACTA2 (alpha-smooth muscle actin); MMP2, MMP9 (matrix metalloproteinases 2 and 9). Normalised against ACTB (beta-actin) reference gene. Data presented as $2^{(-ddCt)}$, relative to Ctrl (calibrator). Mean + SD (n=3-5). Unpaired t-test with Welch's correction (*p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001).

69x62mm (1200 x 1200 DPI)

Figure 7. Comparison of contracted (M-side) and non-contracted (L-side) of clubfoot tissue - complementary data. (A) Demonstrative images of immunohistochemical (IHC) staining and signal detection. Staining of collagen type III and VI, lysyl hydroxylases 1, 2 and 3 (LH1, LH2, LH3). The red areas in the ST (signal threshold) columns represent the positive pixels after thresholding. An image analyser was then used to measure the percentage of the area with a positive signal from the total area. E+ Extracellular positivity, N+ Nuclear positivity, C+ Cytosolic positivity, N/A Not Assessed. Scale bar = 20 μ m. (B) The percentage of COL3, COL6, LH2 and LH3 positive area after IHC signal quantification. LH1 was not detectable. Scatter plots, median with 95% CI (n=10). Paired t-test (**p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001).

178x218mm (243 x 243 DPI)

Figure 8. Proliferation and extracellular collagen type I deposition of contracted clubfoot-derived cells (CF-M) after 7 days of culture without (Ctrl) or with (Fc18) macromolecularly crowded media and different concentrations of minoxidil (MXD). (A) Demonstrative images of extracellular type I collagen deposition (green) and cell density (blue - nuclei) after fluorescent staining. Olympus IX51 microscope, 10 \times objective. Scale bar = 200 μm . (B) Cell proliferation in Ctrl and Fc18 media with different MXD concentrations. Truncated violin plot, Median with IQR (n=30-36). ANOVA, Tukey's test. (C) The amount of extracellular collagen deposited presented as the integrated fluorescence density of extracellular type I collagen normalised to the cell count. Box plot, Median with IQR (n=30-33). Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA, Dunn's test (**p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001, ****p < 0.0001).

178x127mm (243 x 243 DPI)

Figure 9. Relative mRNA expression of genes for collagen and collagen-crosslinking enzymes in clubfoot-derived fibroblasts (CF-M) after 24 hours of cultivation in non-crowded Ctrl or macromolecularly crowded Fc18 media with or without the addition of minoxidil (MXD). Genes of interest: PLOD1, PLOD2, PLOD3 (lysyl hydroxylase 1, 2 and 3); COL1A1, COL1A2 (collagen type I alpha-1 and alpha-2 chains). Normalised against ACTB (beta-actin) reference gene. Data presented as $2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$, relative to Ctrl (calibrator). Mean + SD (n=4). Two-Way ANOVA, Tukey's multiple comparisons test (*p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001, ****p < 0.0001).

139x106mm (1200 x 1200 DPI)

Figure 10. Analysis of collagen matrix deposited by clubfoot-derived (CF-M) cells after 16 days of cultivation in non-crowded Ctrl or macromolecularly crowded Fc18 media with or without minoxidil (MXD) treatment. (A) Long-term collagen deposition was measured by hydroxyproline assay and was normalised to the total protein concentration in the sample. (B) The level of collagen cross-linking was measured as the concentration of pyridinoline and deoxypyridinoline cross-links and is presented relative to the concentration of collagen in the samples. Box plots, Median with IQR (n=6). Two-Way ANOVA, Tukey's multiple comparisons test (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$).

119x68mm (1200 x 1200 DPI)